

Indus Magic

Innovate, Develop & Up Scale Modular, Agile,
Intensified & Continuous Processes & Plants

Highlights of Work done during 2013 - 2016

March 2016

MAGIC (Modular, Agile, Intensified & Continuous) Processes & Plants

CSIR – NCL, IICT, CSMCRI, CLRI, NIIST

Indus Magic

Innovate, Develop & Up Scale Modular, Agile,
Intensified & Continuous Processes & Plants

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Internal Report

Picture from Professor Octave Levenspiel

Modular
AGile
Intensified
Continuous

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MAGIC Demo Lab

Preamble

Together the Indus MAGIC partners have a shared long term vision for fine and specialty chemicals sector: to enable a step change from the current batch manufacturing paradigm to MAGIC manufacturing processes, systems and plants with better quality products at a lower cost, and in a more sustainable manner.

Fine and specialty chemical industry forms the backbone of industrial and agricultural development of India. It caters to several key applications required for maintaining and enhancing quality of life and is going to be increasingly important for India. Indian fine and specialty chemical industry faces many challenges today. It is interesting to note that most of the fine and specialty chemicals are still manufactured in stirred batch reactors (devised centuries ago) operated as batch or semi-batch processes. A paradigm shift is necessary to transform this into new age, efficient and continuous processes and plants.

CSIR's Indus MAGIC program is formulated to address these needs (www.indusmagic.org). It brings chemists and chemical engineers together to work on a large canvas relevant to Indian fine and specialty chemicals sector involving atom efficient process routes (better catalysts, benign reactants and solvents) and enhance product yield and quality. Based on a critical analysis of existing strengths and inputs about the industry needs, the research under the Indus MAGIC program focusses on following concepts:

- Modular reactors/ devices: Modular nature of devices and process equipment will significantly reduce field work and will shrink the time for translating laboratory research to practice. New types of modular reactors and devices as well as corresponding operating strategies are being developed.
- Ability to adopt process changes: Rapid changes in the market requirements demand a step change in ability of process plant to reconfigure and adapt to the market requirements. Efforts are made to extend and to realize flexibility of batch plants into continuous processes and plants.
- Intensified processes: New strategies for intensification and for identification of better process windows are being developed.
- Continuous processes: Developing continuous processes and platforms for variety of key reactions used in manufacturing of fine and specialty chemicals.

Besides CSIR-NCL which is a nodal laboratory for the Indus MAGIC program, four other CSIR labs (IICT, CSMCRI, NIIST and CLRI) are participating in this program. The focus of this Indus MAGIC program is to develop process technologies needed by our industry and to make significant impact on fine and specialty chemicals sector. The kick-off meeting of Indus MAGIC program was held on February 18, 2013. This booklet highlights the key results obtained so far. The approach, facilities and structure established as a part of Indus MAGIC will last much longer and the team hopes that it will MAGICally change the way we manufacture fine and specialty chemicals.

Vivek V. Ranade
Nodal Officer, Indus MAGIC

Overview of Indus MAGIC Program

Indus MAGIC program was initiated for developing modular, agile, intensified and continuous (MAGIC) processes and plants for fine and specialty chemicals industry. The focus is on process intensification (PI). PI may be broadly defined as the ability to obtain better results in terms of purity, selectivity and yield of the desired product by manipulating rates of relevant transport processes so as to enhance process performance (more throughput, better quality, less energy consumption, less waste, safer ...). The MAGIC concepts outlined here need to be developed differently in light of the current status of Indian fine and specialty chemicals industry than the prevailing concepts in the western world. Any such research program needs to involve industries from the beginning. It is essential to create a strong relationship based on mutual trust between scientists and industry doyens. Secondly, it is also essential to involve large number of chemical engineering and process chemistry students in the program to sensitize them with the concepts of MAGIC plants and processes. These students will eventually work in the industry and will facilitate implementation of MAGIC concepts in industry and realize the desired transformation of the way we manufacture fine and specialty chemicals today. The overall structure of the Indus MAGIC program is shown in the following:

The overall program is aimed at:

- Create knowledge base, IP, technology and develop MAGIC processes for fine and specialty chemicals
 - Developing new process windows: Higher temperature; Higher reactant concentration / higher operating pressure; Higher catalyst concentration
 - Better catalysts
 - Better solvents
 - Better process routes
 - Enhancing & intensifying transport processes
- Establish a demo MAGIC plant at NCL
- Create new entrepreneurs, start-up ventures & globally leading fine and specialty chemical industry
- "MAGIC" ally transform Indian fine & specialty chemicals industry

Select appropriate process candidates in consultation with industry

Develop MAGIC process & plant by bringing together process chemistry, reaction engineering & process intensification

Indus Magic

Figures are from Gerven and Stankiewicz, Fundamentals of PI, 2009

Deliver materials and energy at right time & right place

Research

The research undertaken in the Indus MAGIC program was focused on:

- Develop intensified reactors and process equipment
- Develop new process windows
- Convert batch processes to continuous processes
- Develop intensified process separations

The focus is on process intensification (PI). PI may be broadly defined as the ability to obtain significantly better results in terms of purity, selectivity and yield of the desired product by manipulating rates of relevant transport processes so as to enhance process performance (more throughput, better quality, less energy consumption, less waste, safer ...).

Advances in intensified devices including micro-reactors and micro-fluidic devices have created significant hype and awareness about PI in recent decade. The gradual but certain expansion of scope of research and development from micro-devices to milli- or even centi-scale devices is rapidly enhancing potential for adoption in practice.

Research under the Indus MAGIC program focusses on the key drivers of performance enhancement as listed in adjacent table. Key research accomplishments are highlighted here.

	Factors	Tools for MAGIC processes
Material costs	Selectivity, avoiding hot spots, optimal operating conditions	Reactions/ chemistry, Reaction kinetics, intensified mixing, heat & mass transfer devices, novel process windows
Conversion costs	Conversion, smaller equipment, simplified process operations	Integrated heat management, novel process windows, automation
Capital costs	Reducing number of process steps, combining process operations, smaller equipment size	Intensified devices, multifunctional reactors, new process routes/ process windows, novel process control
Time required for commercialization	Complexities in scale-up, extent of customized requirements	Modular (& intensified) equipment, combination of numbering up/ scale-up
Process complexity	Reduced number of process steps, combining process operations	Multifunctional reactors, new process routes/ process windows, wireless control
Product quality	Avoiding hot spots, enhancing selectivity, eliminating impurities	Intensified mixing, heat and mass transfer, better process windows, optimal operating conditions, improved separations, automation
Safety	Avoiding hot spots and run away conditions, inherently safer processes	Intensified mixing, heat and mass transfer, better process windows, integrated heat management, control philosophy
Environmental footprint	Better selectivity, lower solvent requirements	Intensified devices, new process routes/ process windows, automation

Topologically Tubular Reactors

Intensified Reactors

Most of the fine and specialty chemicals are manufactured using stirred tank reactors operated in a batch or semi-batch mode. Despite significant flexibility offered by stirred tanks, the stirred tanks have inherent limitations on their heat and mass transfer performance. The stirred tanks also exhibit a wide distribution of shear rates and internal circulation times which have adverse implications on mixing and mass transfer performance. Heat transfer is usually a limiting factor since heat transfer area per unit volume of reactor is $\sim 10 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$. Therefore for many exothermic reactions, intrinsic chemical reaction rates need to be slowed down in order to be able to carry them in stirred vessels. In the Indus MAGIC program, we have developed “MAGIC tubes” as our reactor platform for intensifying processes.

Tubular (topographically tubular including channels of any cross-section) reactors offer significantly larger heat transfer area compared to stirred reactors. However, tubular reactors usually exhibit undesired residence time distribution. It is essential to overcome these difficulties and transform them into ‘MAGIC’ tubes (suitable as modular, agile, intensified and continuous reactors). We have used various ways to achieve this. One example is of a newly developed passive method of ‘pinching of pipes’. The circular pipe is pinched at regular intervals with alternate direction. The pinching of pipe results changes in flow velocity and direction, which in turn enhances mixing and heat transfer performance. The second example is based on combination of lamellar channel and channel with internals. The newly developed intensified strategies are patented and the reactors based on these concepts are already commercialized.

Design and Performance Aspects: Metallic

- Reactor volumes: 1 ml to 10000 ml (10 L)
- Pressure ratings: 1 bar to 50 bar
- Temperature ratings: - 40 OC to 250 OC
- Synthesis/Production capacity: Lab scale (< 10 g/hr), Bench scale (100 g/hr), Pilot and plant scale (200 kg/day – 2000 kg/day)

Filed patents
Registered designs

Licensed to Amar
Equipment Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai

First indigenously developed and commercialized intensified reactors:
already sold to more than 30 industries; being exported

First of its kind glass lined micro- and tubular reactors; co-developed and being commercialized via GMM Pfäudler

Design and Performance Aspects (Glass-lined)

Reactor volumes: 2 ml to 1000 ml (1 L); Pressure ratings: 1 bar to 10 bar
Temperature ratings: - 20 OC to 250 OC
Heat transfer area per unit volume: 360 – 800 m^2/m^3
Synthesis/Production capacity: Lab scale (< 10 g/hr); Bench scale (100 g/hr)

Indus Magic

Intensifying Reactions

Manufacturing of most of the fine and specialty chemicals involve many fast and exothermic reactions such as nitrations, diazotizations, hydrogenations, oxidations and so on. Conventionally these reactions are carried out in stirred tank reactors operated in a batch or semi-batch mode. Because of inherent limitations of heat transfer area available in stirred reactors, many of these commercially important reactions are carried out with deliberately lowering their rates in order to be able to carry them in stirred reactors. In the Indus MAGIC program, we have developed "MAGIC tubes" as our reactor platform for intensifying processes as discussed earlier. Considering these intensified reactors, it is possible not just to eliminate deliberate reduction in rates but also to further intensify reactions rates by designing appropriate process window (catalyst concentration, reactant concentrations and temperature profiles within the reactor).

In the Indus MAGIC program, we have intensified several important chemical reactions and have developed continuous processes based on these intensified reactions:

- Nitrations
- Diazotizations
- Hydrogenations
- Alkylation
- Arylation
- Halogenation
- Hydrolysis
- Condensation

Intensification Strategies

Enhanced transport processes: small channels, new devices, rotational flows, better solvents ...

Enhanced reaction rates: higher temperature, catalyst/ reactant concentration, multiple dosing, better catalyst

Several disclosures and patents have been filed on the newly developed intensified and continuous processes. Some of these are already translated or being translated to practice.

Continuous nitration of o-xylene

Conventional Process	Intensified Process
T = -5 to 5 C	T > 20 C
Batch time= 8 – 12 hrs	Residence time < 1 min
Conversion = 95% Yield = 93%	Conversion = 99% Yield = 97%
4NOx:3NOx::45:55	4NOx:3NOx::55:45
Mixed acids	Only fuming HNO ₃

Multiple feed locations

Several processes like quinaldines, oxidation of alcohols using TEMPO, continuous nitration of salicylic acid were intensified using multipoint dosing of one of the reactants

Conventional Process	Intensified Process
T = 20 to 40 C	T > 50 C
Batch time= 8 – 16 hrs	Residence time < 1 min
Conversion = 95% Yield = 82%	Conversion = 100% Yield = 97%
Large quantities of solvents and mixed acids	60% less solvents and only fuming HNO ₃

↑ Continuous dinitration of xylenes

Intensified hydrogenation of Cinnamyl aldehyde

Better solvent, higher catalyst concentration of promoter and catalyst, higher T

Continuous Crystallizer Set-up

Crystallization Workstation with FBRM

Process Separations/ Crystallization

Many of the fine and specialty chemicals are sold as solid products. Crystallization – Filtration and Drying are some of the important process operations required to manufacture products of desired quality. It is often necessary to purify the intended product up to desired specifications by distillation or extraction before carrying out crystallization step. Under the Indus MAGIC program, we have investigated extraction and crystallization to improve quality of fine and specialty products of commercial interests. Both, experimental as well as theoretical tools were developed to intensify and improve these process separations.

Crystallization: Batch and Continuous

- Developed computational models and methodology for estimating nucleation and growth kinetics
- Developed models and tools for converting chord length distributions (CLD) measured using FBRM to particle size distributions (PSD)
- Generated solubility and crystallization data for:
 - Para amino phenol – Water
 - Para amino phenol – Methanol
 - Paracetamol – Water
 - Paracetamol – Ethanol
 - Sodium nitrite – Water
 - Malic acid – Water
 - Fumaric acid – Water
- Established continuous plug flow type crystallizer
- Established models and tools for converting batch crystallization to continuous

Commercially Important Focus

- Paracetamol
- Sodium Nitrite
- Para-aminophenol

Towards Industrial Application

- Robust & efficient models
- Proof of concept
- Scale-up issues
- Continuous crystallization

State of the Art Particle Size Characterization

TECHNOFORCE

Collaborating with industry for continuous crystallization

Generic Modeling Recipe

- Estimate critical coefficients
- Configuration specific models
- Optimal operating protocol

Experiments for estimating liquid – liquid equilibrium, distribution coefficients, heat of extraction, liquid – liquid mass transfer coefficients

Distillation & Extraction Facility

Extraction

- Developed effective separation strategies and design data for important products
- Developed separation protocols for purification of para and ortho amino phenols
- Developed separation processes to extract succinic acid and levulinic acid

Set-up for equilibrium studies

Automation and Process Control

Indian fine and specialty chemicals sector, the extent of automation and use of modern process control is rather minimal. Many of these chemicals are manufactured in stirred tank reactors operated in a batch or semi-batch mode. Considering these factors, Indus MAGIC program included a research component on automation and process control. A novel approach for wireless sensing and control was developed with the help of a start-up company, Wiseco Solutions Pvt. Ltd. Specific research on process control strategies and tools was carried out to develop appropriate process control methodology for fine and specialty chemicals industry. Several publications and conference presentations were made based on this research.

Dynamic Modeling & Advanced Process Control

- Developed models for single & multiple esterification reactions with homogeneous & heterogeneous catalysts
 - Reactive batch distillation process from experimental data
 - Simple method for VLE model
- Developed novel time-varying neural network architecture developed for batch and semi-batch processes
- Proposed dynamic optimization methodology
 - Applied to a copolymerization reactor
- Used RNA based genetic algorithms for optimization
- Developed multi-objective optimal control strategy for a batch cooling crystallization process

Process Monitoring Methodologies

- Developed process monitoring methodology based on scaled Principal Component Analysis
- Computer aided solvent design method developed with multi-objective optimization for extraction
- Estimation method for overall mass transfer coefficient in a fast reaction is developed based on neural network model
- Applied these to several case studies

Wireless Sensing and Control

Working with a start-up on developing affordable, accurate and reliable wireless sensing and control solutions for fine and specialty chemicals industry. Key features of this work:

- Conventional sensors and actuators are used
- Developed proprietary wireless IO module and algorithms to establish secure and reliable communication
- SCADA system with HMI is designed in Labview. Data may be accessed from any where via web

First proto-type in market

Water Treatment, Recycle and Reuse

Many fine and specialty chemicals industry are facing severe hardships because of lack of availability of fresh water as well as stringent norms on effluents. A specific research component on intensified treatment of industrial wastewater was undertaken as a part of Indus MAGIC program. A novel, in-line and distributed water treatment methodology based on hydrodynamic cavitation was developed.

A new fluidic device which uses tangential flow for generating cavitation was developed. It has several advantages over conventional devices used for cavitation. Couple of disclosures/ patents on using this device for industrial wastewater treatment have been filed. The effectiveness of the developed methodology was demonstrated for several industrial effluents on bench scale. The know-how has been licensed to a start-up company for field scale trials and commercialization.

Tangential Flow Device for Cavitation

- Unique design: suitable for dirty and solids containing fluids
- Developed internals to manipulate number density and collapse intensity of generated cavities
- Developed design and scale-up guidelines using computational fluid dynamics
- Designed devices up to 100 m³/hr flow rate

Know – how Licensed to

VIVIRA

Cavitation devices are being scaled-up and deployed for field scale trials:

- Distillery spent wash treatment: sugar industry
- Ammonical nitrogen treatment for fisheries and fertilizer industry
- Sewage water treatment plants and cleaning of water bodies: Pune Municipal Corporation
- Distributed effluent treatment for fine and specialty chemicals industry

Organized workshop and brought out a book on wastewater treatment, recycle and reuse

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Computational Modeling

Computational modelling was used to provide key insights underlying development of MAGIC processes and plants for Indian fine and specialty chemicals sector. Classical reaction engineering models, computational fluid dynamics based models and process models were developed and used for designing intensified processes and devices. Several publications and conference presentations were made based on this research. Some of this are briefly highlighted here.

Flow Models for Intensified Devices

- Topologically tubular reactors
 - AMaR family of reactors
 - Pinched tube reactors
 - Helical coil reactors
- Vortex diodes
- Orifices & venturies

Reaction Engineering Models

- Developed CRE methodology for designing MAGIC reactors
 - Design laboratory set-up and operation to ensure no transport limitations
 - Obtain reaction kinetics
 - Reaction calorimetry/ DSC studies to identify safe operating temperature/ conditions
 - Multi-zonal tubular reactor design considering mixing of reactants, axial backmixing, mass and heat transfer
- Developed tools for identifying safe and optimal operating process windows

$$\frac{d^2 C_A}{dZ^2} - Pe_M \frac{dC_A}{dZ} - (Pe_M \cdot \phi^2 \cdot Da) \cdot e^{-\gamma/T} \cdot f(C_A) = 0$$

$$\frac{d^2 T}{dZ^2} - Pe_H \frac{dT}{dZ} - (\beta \cdot Pe_H \cdot \phi^2 \cdot Da) \cdot e^{-\gamma/T} \cdot f(C_A) = -\hat{Q}$$

Developed proof of concepts and translated these to practice via bi-lateral projects with industry partners

Four phase hydrogenation

Nitrations

Aarti Industries Ltd

Yellow dye

Nitration & Photo bromination

Nitrations

Diazotization

ANUPAM RASAYAN INDIA LTD.

RALLIS INDIA LIMITED

Aldol condensation

Cavitation based effluent treatment

Quinaldines

Process, Product & Technologies

“MAGIC”ally Transform Fine & Specialty Chemicals Industry

Work done under the Indus MAGIC program has resulted in developing processes, products and technologies for transforming the way fine and specialty chemicals are manufactured. These developed processes are characterized by enhanced performance in terms of selectivity and yield of the desired products, better safety, lower spatial and environmental foot print and time required for translating from laboratory to practice.

Some of the processes and results developed under the Indus MAGIC program have already been translated to practice. Several bi-lateral projects have been signed based on the proof of concept work carried out under Indus MAGIC program. We are confident that many other industries will adapt “MAGIC” concepts for creating and retaining competitive edge in the global fine and specialty chemicals market.

The processes, products and technologies will make significant contributions to start-up companies as well as to micro – small and medium scale industries. This will also make useful contributions to “Make in India” program launched by Prime Minister of India and will contribute to creation of new jobs and prosperity.

Examples of Performance Enhancement using MAGIC Approach & Developments

- Pendimethylene is a Herbicide
- Developed intensified process with
 - 88% reduction in solvent and
 - 500 times smaller reactor
- Potential **GAME CHANGING** technology

Pendimethylene

Replaced 10000 lit batch reactor by 16 lit MAGIC reactor

Will **transform** MSMEs

Indus Magic

Fluid – Fluid Reactions

Computational modelling was used to provide key insights underlying development of MAGIC processes and plants for Indian fine and specialty chemicals sector. Classical reaction engineering models, computational fluid dynamics based models and process models were developed and used for designing intensified processes and devices. Several publications and conference presentations were made based on this research. Some of this are briefly highlighted here.

Substrate	Conventional Process		MAGIC Process	
	T (°C)	Batch time (min)	T (°C)	Res. time (min)
Salicylic acid	~30	90	> 60	0.8 – 1
Propiophenone	-30	120	10	< 5
Benzaldehyde	0	480	40	< 15
Bromobenzene	55	30	70	< 5
Chlorobenzene	25	180	65	< 4
Fluorobenzene	55	40	30	< 3

Nitrations: MAGIC Approach

- Transformation of batch process in continuous process
- Minimization/elimination of sulfuric acid in the nitrating agent
- Quantitative understanding of parametric effects
- Minimization of solvent quantity and di/tri nitro derivatives
- Optimal combination of reaction temperature and residence time - maximize the conversion and yield of the desired isomer
- Systematic multi-zonal design approach

Nitration of 3-chloroacetophenone with only fuming nitric acid

Diazotizations

- Developed intensified and continuous processes for several industrially relevant diazotizations
- Novel synthesis approach & new reactor types
- Significantly faster rates, better selectivity, lower waste and lower footprint
- Multistep synthesis of azo dyes (Sudan dyes), direct Yellow-11 & 12, Acid red, hydrazines [FC], Pioglitazone [API], quinaldines [Pigment intermediated]

Application example to dyes industry

Developed ability to tailor the color as per requirements

Reactions with Solid Catalyst

Catalysts are involved in the production of more than 80% industrially important chemicals. Recognizing the urgent need to develop cost-effective and environmentally benign methods of converting natural resources into fine and speciality chemicals, Indus MAGIC team focussed on developing replacement of the stoichiometric reactions by the catalytic reactions, application of new catalyst systems and technologies to make the processes environmentally friendly, energy efficient and globally competitive. The team used two pronged strategy: in one, design and development of new catalyst systems for fine and speciality chemicals was undertaken. In the second, commercial catalysts were fine tuned and optimized for developing intensified processes. The work by the MAGIC team covered commercially relevant reactions like hydrogenation, oxidation, esterification, alkylation, aldol condensation and cyclization reactions. As a sample of the work done, some examples are outlined here.

Diphenyl Methane [DPM]

- DPM has applications in perfumery sector
- Heterogeneously catalyzed process is developed to synthesize DPM in an intensified way
- Novel pre-treatment was developed to eliminate induction time observed in these reactions
- Provisional patent has been filed

Catalyst for di-phenyl methane

- Developed a heterogeneously catalyzed process for 4 – methoxy phenol: conventionally polluting processes are used
- Used as antioxidant, stabilizer in ethers, inhibitor, manufacturing of dyes and pharmaceuticals
- Developed recyclable catalyst with methanol as solvent and methylating agent
- Simple separation protocol by distillation and steam stripping

Hydrogenations

- Developed various catalytic hydrogenation processes
 - For replacing FeCl₃ based reduction for MPDSA (dyes sector)
 - Cinnamyl alcohol (perfumery)
 - Para-amino phenol
- Developed novel process windows to intensify reaction rates and to improve selectivity
- Developed designs for glass lined gas inducing impellers for carrying out solid catalyzed gas-liquid reactions

Pilot plant being erected based on proof of concept in Indus MAGIC followed by a bi-lateral project

Industrial Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals

Sunil Joshi, Vivek Ranade

Developed computational models to simulate gas induction and four phase boiling reactors for hydrogenation applications

Indus Magic

Workshop on Industrial Catalysis and Catalytic Processes

Continuous Reaction Calorimeter

Easy to install & operate

Indus MAGIC Reaction Calorimeter

- Total volume < 15 ml
- Temperature range = -20 to 250 OC
- Flow rates = 0.5 ml/min to 50 ml/min
- Multipoint dosing is possible
- Simultaneously 3 fluids can be pumped
- Built-in control system for utility
- Multipoint temperature sensing is possible
- Completely plug and play kind of system
- Can be used as a flow reactor
- Possibility to take samples at different locations

The system can be used for **batch operation** as well. Can be operated in **adiabatic** as well as **isothermal** modes

Patents filed (IN2105DEL2012, PCT/IN2013/000419)

Software Features

- In-house developed software
- Advanced data analysis algorithms
- Wireless data transfer
- LABVIEW based Software
- Acquisition at 100 Hz
- Built-in post processing with various filters and wavelet de-noising
- Multipoint data acquisition
- Real time estimation of enthalpy

MAGIC Lab

Inaugurated by Hon'ble
Minister of Science and
Technology, Dr Harsh Vardhan

February 2016

MAGIC Process & Product Laboratory

Review of MAGIC Lab by Dr Harsh Vardhan

Indus Magic
Innovate, Develop & Up Scale Modular, Agile, Intensified & Continuous Processes & Plants

Create knowledge base, IP, technology and develop Modular, Agile, Intensified and Continuous [MAGIC] processes & plants for fine and specialty chemicals

Indus CPI - Established Industry Consortium on Process Intensification [Indus CPI]

Developed and licensed metallic and glass lined reactors

Established MAGIC demonstration facility at CSIR - NCL

Developed proof of concepts and translated these to practice via bi-lateral projects with industry partners

VINATI ORGANICS LIMITED
Four phase hydrogenation

Nitrations
Aarti Industries Ltd

Yellow dye
ALPS

Nitration & Photo bromination
RALLIS INDIA LIMITED

Diazotization
ANEPAM RASAYAN INDIA LTD.

Quinaldines
VIJAY CHEMICALS

Aldol condensation
asiarpaints

vivira
Cavitation based effluent treatment

"MAGIC" ally transform fine & specialty chemicals industry

West side view: utility island/ effluent storage

North - west side view: assembly workshop

South side view

MAGIC Process & Product
Lab: Outside Views

Indus Magic

Process Hall & Product Studio

MAGIC Process & Product Lab

Process Hall: Houses MAGIC components and bench scale continuous plants
Tall & normal process areas [> 4000 sq. ft.]

Pilot scale WFE (Wiped Film Evaporator]

Tall area region

Module Design

- Compact design with integrated piping & instrumentation
- Replaceable feed tanks with balances
- Manual or automated mode of operation
- Internal exhaust
- Dedicated HMI per module

Reactor bay with AMaR3 Reactor

Water treatment bench scale set-up

Helical coil tubular reactor + bubble column reactor on first floor
Typical Reaction Bay

Member Login

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Indus Magic

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www.indusmagic.org

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CSIR Team

Indus CPI

Indus Magic

Indus MAGIC is an acronym for Innovate, develop and up-scale MAGIC [modular, agile, intensified and continuous] processes and plants. This Indus MAGIC research program of CSIR is formulated based on critical analysis and understanding of the needs of Indian fine and specialty chemical industry. Specialty/ fine chemical industry forms the backbone of industrial and agricultural development of India. Over the years, the industry has evolved from a basic chemical producer to knowledge intensive industry. The industry also exhibited healthy growth. To fulfill the demands for addressing hither expectations of a rapidly developing India, the grow at nearly double the rate of growth of over magnitude of projected expansion and increase research and technology inputs to support and research program is planned as a first step to

Accomplishments so far

[Read More](#)

Processes, Products & Know – how

More than 20 Bi – lateral projects originated from Indus MAGIC work

Spin-out companies

Publications/ patents/ disclosures/ conference presentations

Output	Achieved so far
Journal Publications/ book chapters	>125
Books	2
Disclosures/ patents	~ 35
Lab scale processes (PoC)	> 50
Students/ PA	> 100
Spin-out companies	1 + collaborating with other
Benefit to MSME	~ 200
Designs registered	2
Conference presentations	> 125
Number of workshops conducted	~ 10

Touched several fine and specialty chemicals industries/ created awareness of paradigm shift/ developed MAGIC as potential game changing technology

Established industry consortium on process intensification at CSIR – NCL, IICT and CSMCRI

Indus CPI

Industrial Consortium on Process Intensification

Indus MAGIC Accomplishments

Workshops for Industrial Chemists and Engineers

Workshops for industry practitioners are regularly organized as a part of its large program on developing MAGIC (modular, agile, intensified and continuous) processes and plants. These workshops are focussed on specific themes relevant to fine and specialty chemicals industry and bring out various facets that would help to overcome several of long standing industrial issues. The faculty for the workshop is handpicked from the academia, research laboratories, user industry besides the Indus MAGIC team. Every effort is made to bring out several case studies to illustrate the advantages of MAGIC concepts for enhancing performance. Various sessions are planned to convey state of the art on various themes with adequate information on design approaches and selection of appropriate strategies and equipment. The audience comprises of representatives from the members of Indus CPI (Industry consortium on process intensification), large number of practicing engineers/ process chemists and managers and chemical engineering faculty/ students. More than 200 MSME's are touched through these workshops.

Several exhibitor's stalls are organized to present the state of the art

Training

List of Workshops Conducted so far

- Indus Water [Industrial Water Treatment, Recycle & Reuse]/ June 2012 (NCL)
- Indus CaP [Industrial catalysis & catalytic processes]/ December 2012 (NCL)
- 'Organic Process Research & Development' with Scientific Update, April 2013 (NCL)
- Indus CoP [Intensifying & up-scaling of continuous processes], December 2013 (NCL)
- 'Organic Process Research & Development' with Scientific Update, December 2014 (NCL)
- Indus BCP [Benign Catalytic Processes], May 2015 (CSMCRI)
- Indus APC [Industrial Automation and Process Control], June 2015 (NCL)
- Indus CoP [Process intensification & continuous processes], December 2015 (NCL)
- Needs of Chemical Industry: The role of Research Institutions, February 2016 (IICT)

Indus Water

Industrial Wastewater Treatment, Recycle & Reuse

Indus APC

Industrial Automation and Process Control

Indus BCP

Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine & Specialty Chemicals

SCIENTIFIC
UPDATE

Indus CaP

Innovate, Develop & Up-scale Catalytic Processes for Fine & Specialty Chemicals

Indus CoP

Intensifying & Up-scaling of Continuous Processes

Informative
Talks

Lab visits

Indus Magic

Training

List of Proof of Concepts developed under Indus MAGIC

No	Title	Institute
1	Process for 4-nitro-o-xylene & 3-nitro-o-xylene	CSIR – NCL
2	Process for Nitrobenzene	CSIR – NCL
3	Process for mono nitro-chlorobenzene	CSIR – NCL
4	Process for mono nitro-bromobenzene	CSIR – NCL
5	Process for Mono nitro-fluorobenzene	CSIR – NCL
6	Process for nitro-m-chloroacetopnenone	CSIR – NCL
7	Process for nitro-p-chloroacetopnenone	CSIR – NCL
8	Process for nitro-Propiophenone	CSIR – NCL
9	Process for m-nitro benzaldehyde	CSIR – NCL
10	Process for nitro cumene	CSIR – NCL
11	Continuous synthesis of Phenyl hydrazine and its derivatives	CSIR – NCL
12	Process for two step continuous preparation of sodium hypochlorite	CSIR – NCL
13	Process for continuous nitration of Pendimethylene	CSIR – NCL
14	Process for continuous synthesis and isolation of Quinaldine	CSIR – NCL
15	Process for continuous flow synthesis of Silver nanoparticles	CSIR – NCL
16	Process for 4-methoxyphenol from hydroquinone	CSIR – NCL
17	Continuous process for Morpholine	CSIR – NCL
18	Process for Diethyl Phthalate	CSIR – NCL
19	Process for 3 Methyl Pentenone (MPO)	CSIR – NCL
20	Continuous process for Pentaerythritol	CSIR – NCL
21	Continuous process for m-cresol	CSIR – NCL
22	Continuous process for 1-Nitro Naphthalene	CSIR – NCL
23	Synthesis Coumarin Derivatives from Phenolic Acetates and Acrylates	CSIR – NCL
24	Oxidative esterification of aldehydes with alkylarenes or alcohols using TBHP as an oxidant	CSIR – NCL
25	Novel eco-friendly, cost effective, catalytic process for the synthesis of Tertiary butyl phenol (TBP)	CSIR – NCL
26	Synthesis of quinoline carboxylates by Rhodium-catalyzed ortho C–H bond activation of arylamines	CSIR – NCL
27	Synthesis of Propyl Acetate by catalytic reactive distillation	CSIR – NCL
28	Novel eco-friendly, cost effective, autocatalytic process for the synthesis of tributyl citrate	CSIR – NCL
29	Process for synthesis of p-Methoxyacetophenone (4-MAP)	CSIR – NCL
30	Newer Biocoagulants and Intensified Coagulation Process for Wastewater Treatment	CSIR – NCL
31	Activated carbons & process for removing pollutants from aqueous/ organic streams using Cassia fistula	CSIR – NCL
32	Process Development - Polyaluminum chloride	CSIR – NCL
33	Vortex diodes as effluent treatment devices	CSIR – NCL
34	Spherical Activated Carbon from Resins	CSIR – NCL
35	Process for synthesis of diphenyl methane (DPM)	CSIR – NCL
36	Intensifying Hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde to cinnamyl alcohol	CSIR – NCL
37	Synthesis of methyl phenyl carbamate from aniline and dimethyl carbonate	CSIR – NCL
38	Synthesis of styrene oxide from styrene	CSIR – CSMCRI
39	Process for the preparation of ring-opened glyceryl ricinoleates, epoxy alkyl ricinoleates, and ring-opened alkyl ricinoleates from epoxidized castor oil	CSIR – CSMCRI
40	Process for the synthesis of 3-methyl-5-phenylpentanol (Mefrosol)	CSIR – CSMCRI
41	Process for the preparation of γ -valerolactone by catalytic hydrogenation of levulinic acid	CSIR – CSMCRI
42	Chemo- and regioselective synthesis of arylated γ -valerolactones from biomass derived levulinic	CSIR – CSMCRI
43	Oxidation of n-octanol to octyloctanoate using bromide and bromate couple	CSIR – CSMCRI
44	Synthesis of α -hexyl cinnamaldehyde (hexyl cinnamal) from n-octanal and benzaldehyde	CSIR – CSMCRI
45	Continuous process for the preparation of 2,3-dihydrofuran from cis-1,4-but-2-enediol	CSIR – CSMCRI
46	Synthesis of Jasminaldehyde from n-heptanal and benzaldehyde	CSIR – CSMCRI
47	Synthesis of β -bromostyrene from styrene bromohydrin	CSIR – CSMCRI
48	Resolution of metallohelicates	CSIR – CSMCRI
49	Synthesis of Di-octyl phthalate by heterogeneous acid catalysis	CSIR – CSMCRI
50	Synthesis of α -pinene oxide from α -pinene in aqueous phase	CSIR – CSMCRI
51	Process for the preparation of cyclamenaldehyde	CSIR – CSMCRI
52	Process for preparation of cuminaldehyde using tert-butyl hydroperoxide as oxidant	CSIR – CSMCRI
53	Process for the selective hydrogenation of methyl ricinoleate to ricinoleyl alcohol	CSIR – CSMCRI
54	Development of catalytic process for the preparation of vanillin from isoeugenol	CSIR – CSMCRI
55	Continuous process for the preparation of 1-octene from castor oil derived 2-octanol	CSIR – CSMCRI
56	Catalytic Process for Single Step Synthesis of Glycidol from Glycerol	CSIR – IICT
57	Catalytic Process for Selective Synthesis of Glycerol Carbonate from Glycerol and Urea	CSIR – IICT
58	Process for para-tert-Butyl benzoic acid (PTBBA)	CSIR – IICT
59	Process for para-tert-Butyl methyl benzoate (PTBMB)	CSIR – IICT
60	Process for para-tert-butyl Toluene (PTBT)	CSIR – IICT

List of Bi – lateral projects resulted from PoC developed under Indus MAGIC

Description	Other details	Industry
Indus CPI consortium	NCL	Various
Indus CPI consortium	IICT	Various
Indus CPI consortium	CSMCRI	Various
Licensed intensified reactors to Amar Equipment Pvt Ltd and the products with CSIR – NCL logo are in the market. The product line is helping several industries to evaluate and implement continuous processing	The company has sold nearly Rs one crore worth of the products so far. Reactors are protected by filing patents	Amar Equipment
MoU has been signed for development of glass lined intensified reactors with GMM Pfaudler. The prototype units have been fabricated and are being tested at CSIR - NCL	This is the first of its kind glass lined intensified reactors. A patent has been filed.	GMM
Developed effluent treatment methodology based on hydrodynamic cavitation. Developed a cavitation device. Patents are filed to protect the developed IP. Technology is licensed to a spin-out company for commercialization.	Vivira Process Technologies Pvt. Ltd. has been founded under the SES scheme. The company has received a BIG grant of BIRAC for proving the technology on field scale.	VIVIRA Process Technologies
Developed proof of concept for a low pressure hydrogenation process for an important intermediate. Developed several innovations and filed patents.	Signed a bi-lateral project with industry for establishing commercial plant. The work on development of basic engineering package for the commercial plant has started.	Vinati Organics
Developed bench scale processes for alkyl toluene: catalytic alkylation	Signed bi-lateral project with industry. Basic engineering report is completed and delivered.	Vinati Organics
Developed bench scale processes for oxidation of alkyl toluene to corresponding acids	Signed bi-lateral project with industry. Basic engineering report is completed.	Vinati Organics
Developed bench scale processes for esterification of substituted aromatic acids to corresponding esters	Signed bi-lateral project with industry. Basic engineering report is in progress.	Vinati Organics
Developed continuous process for nitration. Proved concept on lab scale, pilot plant is working at the client's site, further scale-up work is in progress	A 5000 tpa plant is envisaged after establishing successful pilot trials.	Acetochem
Developed a continuous process for diazotization. Proved concept on lab scale. Pilot plant trials are nearing completion.	5000 tpa plant is envisaged. CSIR team will contribute for scale-up if needed.	Anupam Rasayan
Developed continuous flow nitration process. The pilot experiments are complete. Commercial scale reactor design is in progress.	Signed and completed bi-lateral project. Performance has been verified at pilot scale.	Aarti
Continuous flow reactor for the commercial scale production of two products is designed and is under fabrication for commercial scale production. Pilot scale reactor has been in operation since last 6 months.	Signed and completed consultancy project.	Aarti
Styrene epoxide	Know-how & process licensed	Asian Azoles
Developed a continuous process based on nitration. Pilot plant is being established at the client's site.	Signed and completed bi-lateral projects.	Rallis India Ltd.
Developed a photobromination approach for the synthesis of a mono-bromoester. Pilot plant is established at the client's site.	Signed and completed bi-lateral projects.	Rallis India Ltd. (R&D)
Demonstrated the continuous flow processes at lab scale	Signed and completed consultancy projects	Tagros Ltd.
Developed and demonstrated a laboratory scale continuous process based on acetaldehyde	As a part of consortium	Asian Paints
Development of continuous processes	Signed consultancy project	UPL
Set-up continuous flow chemistry laboratory and convert batch to continuous processes	Signed consultancy project	Jay Chemicals
Development of a design approach for multi-step flow process involving hypobromite	Signed consultancy project	Hikal Ltd.

List of Bi – lateral projects resulted/ being discussed from PoC developed under Indus MAGIC (continued)

Description	Other details	Industry
Developed continuous flow condensation followed by reduction for the synthesis of intermediates for pigments. Lab scale demonstration is complete.	Completed bi-lateral project	Vijay Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.
Process Development for synthesis of important derivatives of acetophenone. Process demonstration was given at pilot scale (20 kg) 4-MAP with purity >99.2%	Completed the project. Scale-up is in progress.	Hari Om Chemicals
Developed a modified process for 1,2 PDO based on crude bioglycerol. The catalyst was developed under the NMITLI program. Further work was carried out under Indus MAGIC.	Signed MoU with Sud Chemie for commercial manufacturing of catalyst. Tested catalyst manufactured by Sud Chemie. Discussing with 2 – 3 potential industries.	Godrej, Multiorganics, Caratino
Develop a proof of concept for the continuous synthesis of esters using reactive distillation	Signed MoU. Further discussions are in progress.	Herman Finochem Ltd
Advice on treatment of waste water	Discussing the consulting project	Spak Organochem
Training and development of a design approach for multi-step flow process for the production of agrochemicals.	Discussing the consulting project	Syngenta
Batch to continuous processes for nitrations	Discussing the project	GSP Crops
Continuous processes for nitrations	Discussing the project	Dynemic Chemicals
Continuous processes for nitrations	Discussing the project	Maksons Ltd.
Continuous nitration of various substrates	Discussing the project	Deepak Nitrite Ltd.
Working on crystallization of NaNO ₂ : developing continuous crystallizer and avoiding needle shape crystals.	Discussing the project	Deepak Nitrite Ltd.
Developed a process for large scale synthesis of nanoparticles. Demonstrated for the production of 20 g scale.	Tech transfer is under discussion	Nanoxpert Pvt. Ltd.
Grignard reactions in continuous reactors	Discussing the project	Wanbury Ltd.
Bu Li chemistry in continuous reactors	Discussing the project	Biocon
Developed a lab scale (20 g) process for Vinylidene fluoride from HCFC-142B	Technology transfer is under discussion	Gujarath Fluorine
Developed an improved process for styrene oxide using recyclable urea-derivative	Process under evaluation at the client end	Aquila Organics
Developed an improved process for styrene oxide by using the aqueous phase effluent generated to have better environmental foot print	Process under discussions	Atul Limited
Developing a process for 2,3-dihydrofuran from 1,4-butane/butenediol	As part of the consortium project	Aether Industries Ltd.
Developed process for castor oil derivatives (methoxylated castor polyol, methoxy methyl ricinoleate and epoxy methyl ricinoleate)	Prepared at 0.5 Kg scale and the products are evaluated at the industry end	Jayant Agro Organics Ltd.
Developed process for Mefrosol	The product is being tested at the industry end (including separation issues)	Aquila Organics
Developing process for α -hexyl cinnamaldehyde	Prepared at 100 g scale and the sample sent to industry for testing	Aquila Organics

Already received more than Rs 4 Crores from industry and agreements signed for additional Rs 5 Crores in the form of remaining installments/ royalty. The MAGIC facility established at CSIR – NCL and developed proof of concepts have potential to significantly change face of fine and specialty chemicals industry besides generating revenues to CSIR

Start-up via SES scheme: founded in February 2015 @ NCL Innovation Park

VIVIRA

Multiphase flow
Process Intensification
Optimization & Scale-up

About

- Start-up founded by experts from national labs and academia
- Focus on developing technologies based on advanced devices & products for performance enhancement
- Licensed know-how for commercializing vortex diodes from CSIR – NCL

Key Advantages

- Unique blend of domain expertise, understanding of customer needs and rich basket of products and modeling tools to develop “right” solutions
- Proven ability to execute large projects and realizing performance enhancement
- Tremendous scope to leverage VIVIRA for achieving productivity enhancements

Recipient of BIG Project

Offerings

- Hydrodynamic cavitation based products for process intensification
- Solutions for distributed and in-line effluent treatment
- Solutions for deriving value from waste streams
- Solutions for process intensification and scale-up

Field scale trials are underway in industries

www.vivira.in

Working with a Start-up to Develop Wireless Sensing and Control Solutions

A start-up founded by IITB alumni (www.wiseco.in)

Unique Offerings

- Customized process control solution with through understanding of the underlying process
- Customized hardware and software solution for process control to meet unique requirements
- Wireless communication between plant to control room: requires only local wiring
- Provision of data processing software to analyse the data in variety of easy to use ways
- Provision of web based application to store data on remote web server

Indus Magic

Offers unique opportunity to harness state of the art sensing and control solutions to realize MAGIC manufacturing facilities

Publications/ Patents/ Disclosures/ Presentations

Publications/ patents/ disclosures/ conference presentations based on work done under Indus MAGIC

Books

Summary of Indus MAGIC Output

Category	Number
Book chapters	18
Journal papers	More than 125
Patents/ disclosures	More than 35
Conference presentations	More than 125

Edited a special issue on **Process Intensification** of Indian Chemical Engineer

Indus Magic

See Annexure 2 for complete list of publications/ presentations

Publications/ Patents/
Disclosures/ Presentations

The long journey of MAGICally transforming the way we manufacture fine and specialty chemicals in India has just begun. The Indus MAGIC team believes that the developed work & results may be used as a platform with active partnerships with industry and various industry associations like Indian Chemical Council for realizing the desired step change.

The Indus MAGIC program is focused on developing products and processes needed by our industries. Efforts were made to involve key stakeholders right from the beginning. The Indus MAGIC team has accomplished significant results in last three years as outlined in this report. The team was able to develop laboratory scale proof of concepts of **more than 50 products/ processes**. **More than twenty bi-lateral projects** have already been signed or completed based on the work done under the Indus MAGIC program. **More than 35 patents/ disclosures** have been filed. **More than 100 journal publications, and two books** have been published based on the work done so far. **One start-up company** has been founded for commercializing the cavitation based water treatment technology developed in Indus MAGIC. While the output and outcome from the Indus MAGIC is quite satisfactory, it is important to ponder on how to leverage this to make much larger impact on fine and specialty chemicals industry.

Most of the fine and specialty chemicals are still manufactured using batch or semi-batch processes. It is essential to examine new and better process chemistries, as well as new ways of translating these process chemistries in practice to establish and to retain competitive edge (despite disadvantaged position with respect to raw materials). Many of these fine and specialty chemicals industries are family-owned and closely held. It is a hope that as a new generation takes over, the fine and specialty chemicals sector will start getting a 'make over' by undertaking modernization. Several key challenges such as rigid mind set and limited ability to take risks of the industry remain to be resolved.

Indus MAGIC team also needs to address issues like lack of understanding of key issues controlling commercial exploitation of new ideas and inadequate collaboration between process chemists and chemical engineers. The Indus MAGIC program has initiated significant collaborations between chemists and engineers which need to be strengthened further in coming years. This will lead to more enlightened use of MAGIC concepts in practice.

Another important issue which constrains adoption of new technologies and subsequent growth of fine and specialty chemicals industry is lack of availability of talent. It is important to highlight the role of fine and specialty chemical industry in determining quality of life since that is the only way to attract excellent students to chemical engineering and process chemistry fields. Programs like Indus Scholar initiated by the Indus MAGIC team will hopefully provide a platform which may be expanded further. The MAGIC processes and plants, which advocate compact and modular plants, can in some respects change the image of harsh environment in chemical industry. Modernization of industry based on focused research on MAGIC concepts will help to attract excellent students to this profession and create passion about making substantial impact on quality of life via MAGIC concepts.

It is essential for industry and research institutes/universities to work together to facilitate and to strengthen 'modernization' drive. Some help and incentives for modernization from the Government will be most welcome. Despite some of these challenges, the time is now ripe to adopt new technologies and we hope that Indus MAGIC work will make useful and significant contributions to fine and specialty chemicals sector in the coming years.

Closing Remarks

 Vivek V. Ranade
 Nodal Officer, Indus MAGIC

Annexure 1: Process Notes

Process for continuous nitration of o-xylene

Executive Summary

- A process for 1,2-dimethyl-4-nitrobenzene based on nitration of o-xylene is developed.
- 1,2-dimethyl-4-nitrobenzene (4-NOX) finds application in the synthesis of riboflavin (vitamin B12), high-performance polyurethane resin, and herbicides.
- The conventional process using a nitrating mixture comprising of H₂SO₄ and fuming HNO₃ leads to higher selectivity for isomer 1,2-dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene (3-NOX) over the isomer 4-NOX. It also generates a non-negligible quantity of dinitro derivatives of o-xylene.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 4-NOX compared to that towards 3-NOX.

Background

The current demand for 4-NOX in India is about 900 TPA, of which more than 60% is met through imports. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 4 NOX have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion with greater than 96% selectivity of mono-nitro derivatives (compared to ~80% with the conventional process) and mole ratio of 4-NOX:3-NOX as 55:45 (compared to 45:55 with the conventional process). The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Tested at greater than 50 lit/day scale. Scale-up approach is ready. Reactor designs for producing 1-5 TPD of 4NOX are ready.

Patents: WIPO Patent Application WO/2015/011729

Publications: Sharma, Y.; Joshi, R. A. and Kulkarni, A. A. (2015), *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 19 (9), 1138

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of benzene

Executive Summary

- A process for nitrobenzene based on nitration of benzene is developed.
- Nitrobenzene is consumed in the production of aniline, which is a precursor to rubber chemicals, pesticides, dyes (particularly azo dyes), explosives, and pharmaceuticals.
- The conventional process using a nitrating mixture comprising of H_2SO_4 and fuming HNO_3 . It generates a non-negligible quantity of dinitro derivatives of benzene.
- The developed process is based on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent with catalytic sulphuric acid and leads to higher selectivity towards mono-nitrobenzene.

Background

Use of high amount of sulphuric is general approach for conventional batch process. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid with catalytic amount of sulphuric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at high temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Maintain an adiabatic condition in the reactor that ensures the use of heat of reaction for sustained continuous flow nitration
- Another alternative is to use high temperature isothermal condition but that may not economically compete with the adiabatic mode
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield. Optimal process parameters for enhancing yield and complete consumption of used fuming nitric acid have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99% yield of mono-nitrobenzene with less than 0.5% dinitro derivatives. Sulphuric acid was used in catalytic amount and used fuming nitric acid was completely consumed. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Tested at greater than 76 lit/day scale. Scale-up approach is ready.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of chlorobenzene

Executive Summary

- A process for 1-chloro-4-nitro-benzene based on nitration of chlorobenzene is developed.
- Chloro-nitro-benzene is used in the production of intermediates for azo and sulfur dyes, corrosion inhibitors, pigments, agricultural, pharmaceuticals, photo chemicals, rubber chemicals, and insecticides.
- The conventional process using a nitrating mixture comprising of H₂SO₄, acetic anhydride or BF₃ catalyst with HNO₃ leads to different selectivity for 2 and 4 isomer of chloro-nitro-benzene.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 1-chloro-4-nitrobenzene compared to that towards 1-chloro-2-nitrobenzene.

Background

Depending on the different solvent system, o:p ratio of chloro-nitro-benzene changes in range of 0.24 to 0.76. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer at near isothermal conditions. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 1-chloro-4-nitrobenzene have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99% conversion with greater than 69% selectivity of 1-chloro-4-nitrobenzene. The by-product formation (dinitro derivatives) is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed.

Publication: Sharma Y. and Kulkarni, A. A. (2016) Continuous flow nitration of benzene and halobenzenes (*Manuscript under preparation*)

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of bromobenzene

Executive Summary

- A process for 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene based on nitration of bromobenzene is developed.
- Nitrobromobenzene is useful for drug manufacturing for hypnotic, sedative and antiemetic feature.
- Conventional process using a nitrating mixture comprising of H₂SO₄, acetic anhydride or BF₃ catalyst with HNO₃ leads to different selectivity for 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene and 1-bromo-2-nitrobenzene.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene.

Background

Depending on the different solvent system, o:p isomer ratio of bromo-nitro-benzene changes in range of 0.14 to 0.60. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion with greater than 92% selectivity of 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene. The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Tested at greater than 86 lit/day scale.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of fluorobenzene

Executive Summary

- A process for fluoro-nitro-benzene based on nitration of fluorobenzene is developed.
- Nitro-fluorobenzene is used as antiarrhythmic, antihypertensive and antiischemic drug agent, also it is in demand as an intermediate for antioxidant for rubber and anti-leprosy drug – Dapsone.
- The conventional process using a nitrating mixture comprising of H_2SO_4 , acetic anhydride or BF_3 catalyst with HNO_3 leads to different selectivity for 2 and 4 isomer of fluoro- nitro-benzene.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 1-fluoro-4-nitrobenzene compared to that towards 1-fluoro-2-nitrobenzene.

Background

Depending on the different solvent system, o/p ratio of fluoro-nitro-benzene changes in range of 0.06 to 0.37. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 1-fluoro-4-nitrobenzene have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion with greater than 87% selectivity of 1-fluoro-4-nitrobenzene. The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status: Laboratory scale process developed. Tested at greater than 86 lit/day scale. Scale-up approach is ready.

Publication: Sharma Y. and Kulkarni, A. A. (2016) Continuous flow nitration of benzene and halobenzenes (*Manuscript under preparation*)

Contact: Dr Amol A Kulkarni: +91 20 25902153: aa.kulkarni@ncl.res.in

CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of 3-chloroacetophenone

Executive Summary

- A process for 5-chloro-2-nitroacetophenone (5-chloro-2-NAcPh) based on nitration of 3-chloroacetophenone is developed.
- 5-chloro-2-nitroacetophenone is an intermediate to synthesize antimitotic antitumor agents.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 5-chloro-2-NAcPh.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 97% conversion with greater than 56.4% selectivity of 5-chloro-2-nitroacetophenone. Besides this, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed.

Process for continuous nitration of 4-chloroacetophenone

Executive Summary

- A process for 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone based on nitration of 4-chloroacetophenone is developed.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone with 4-chlorobenzoic acid as side product.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion with greater than 40.30% selectivity of 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone. 4-chlorobenzoic acid forms as an oxidized by-product. The process can be made selective for nitration alone but at lower extent of conversion. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of Propiophenone

Executive Summary

- A process for m-Nitropropiophenone based on nitration of Propiophenone is developed.
- Propiophenone derivatives are important intermediates for the preparation of many drugs and organic compounds, used for ephedrine production, fragrance enhancer and polymer sensitizer.
- Typical batch process involves use of nitrating mixture (with large quantity of sulfuric acid) at a reaction temperature of -10°C with minimum 3 to 4 hours of reaction time.
- The developed process involves use of only fuming nitric acid in a flow system to get desired m-Nitropropiophenone isomer at higher temperature and sufficiently shorter residence time.

Background

Literature lists many examples where m-Nitropropiophenone derivatives are used for the synthesis of biologically active molecules. Though this derivative is used in many API synthesis not much literature is available on efficient synthesis route. Conventional procedure involves use of large quantities of sulfuric acid rather than using stoichiometric quantity and also lower temperature required for the batch procedure is very energy intensive. Present process turns out to be very efficient removing the demerits of conventional approach.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion (compared to ~80% with the conventional process) and mole ratio of 2-nitro to 3-nitro Propiophenone as 1:1.7. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent). Also the current procedure consumes less energy since reaction is done at higher temperature and much safer compared to batch (due to small reaction volumes involved)

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Scale-up approach is ready.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of Benzaldehyde

Executive Summary

- A process for m-Nitrobenzaldehyde on nitration of Benzaldehyde is developed.
- Nitro derivatives of Benzaldehyde find application in dyes, pesticides, pharmaceutical drugs and optical materials etc. Nitrobenzaldehyde also serves as a raw material for the preparation of benzodiazepines and other cardiovascular drugs of the dihydropyridine group.
- Conventional batch process involves mixing of Benzaldehyde with nitrating mixture and reaction temperature to be maintained between -5°C to 15°C.
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards m-Nitrobenzaldehyde compared to batch process in much shorter reaction time.

Background

Process for nitration of Benzaldehyde is very exothermic reaction usually involving long reaction time and contains many waste handling issues due to use of nitrating mixture. Process developed here by using flow method and fuming nitric acid easily overcomes pitfalls of conventional process.

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent in topologically tubular reactor and other in house made devices with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

Reaction scheme for nitration of benzaldehyde using fuming nitric acid

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and fuming nitric acid at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards m-nitrobenzaldehyde have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion and mole ratio of m-nitro to o-nitro Benzaldehyde almost 75:25. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Scale-up approach is ready.

Publications: Sharma et al. (2014), *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 53, 1916; Ranade et al. (2015) *Chem. Eng. J.*

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous nitration of cumene

Executive Summary

- A process for 2-nitrocumene based on nitration of cumene is developed.
- The conventional process using a nitrating mixture comprising of H_2SO_4 and fuming HNO_3 leads to higher selectivity for isomer 4-NC (93%) over the isomer 2-NC (7%).
- Hydrogenised product of nitrocumene (NC) to cumidine is an industrially important reaction. It is a versatile chemical intermediate that has applications in dyes, pharmaceuticals, and herbicides
- The developed process is based only on fuming nitric acid as the nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards 2-NC (20%) compared to that towards conventional batch (7-23%).

Process description

The developed process uses fuming nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a topologically tubular reactor with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

The key process steps are:

- This is a two phase system. Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature and excellent mass transfer helps to improve the conversion.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 98% conversion with greater than 77% selectivity of mono-nitro derivatives and mole ratio of 2-NC : 4-NC = 20:80. The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent).

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Continuous synthesis of Phenyl hydrazine and its derivatives

Executive Summary

- A process for phenyl hydrazine and its derivative based on diazotization of aniline followed by coupling with L-Ascorbic acid to form lactone intermediate and hydrolysis of this lactone intermediate to phenyl hydrazine is developed.
- Phenyl hydrazine finds application as intermediate in the synthesis of various dyes and pharmaceuticals particularly in tryptamine drugs, which is used in the treatment of migraine and cluster headache, used to induce acute haemolytic anaemia in studies examining the hematopoietic system and to prepare agrochemicals.
- The conventional process uses sodium sulfite in the presence of sodium hydroxide to reduce the diazonium salt, but the sodium sulfite solution contains an excess of alkali, a black tar tends to form when the solution is warmed, and very little phenyl hydrazine is obtained and Phenyl hydrazine is also obtained by using zinc dust and acetic acid following the reduction with sodium sulfite. But no improvement in the quality or quantity of the product was obtained by using zinc and acetic acid. The developed process is based only on L-Ascorbic acid as reducing agent and leads to Lactone intermediate followed by hydrolysis to form Phenyl Hydrazine

Background

Of the top 200 selling pharmaceuticals in recent years, 20% of the five membered heterocyclic ring systems are pyrazoles or indoles. These motifs are usually derived from monosubstituted hydrazines either by condensation with 1,3- dicarbonyl to provide pyrazoles or by fisher indole synthesis. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process.

Process description

The developed process uses L-Ascorbic Acid as reducing agent in a tubular reactor.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and using L-Ascorbic Acid as reducing agent at 0°C temperature
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 99.5% conversion with greater than 75% selectivity of phenyl hydrazine (compared to $\sim 45\%$ with the conventional process). The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small spatial (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental friendly.

Technology status: Lab scale process is ready.

Publications: Moolya, S.; Joshi, R. A. and Kulkarni A. A. (2016) Continuous flow multi-step synthesis of hydrazines and optimization (*Under preparation*)

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous preparation of sodium hypochlorite

Executive Summary

- Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) finds application for water purification. It is used on a large scale for surface purification, bleaching, odor removal, nerve agent neutralization, endodontics, stain removal and water disinfection.
-
- The process uses chlorine gas for its reaction with 10% NaOH to form Sodium Hypochlorite. The strength of hypochlorite can vary from 2 - 12% w/v.

Process description

A process is developed for continuous flow synthesis of sodium hypochlorite via reacting chlorine with 10% NaOH. The reaction temperature is maintained about 5 °C and the residence time was varied to generate hypochlorite of different strengths. The maximum residence time was less than 5 min. The solution is stable if maintained at lower temperatures. However the strength of hypochlorite decreases with increasing storage temperature as well as the storage time.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves 2 to 12% w/v of Sodium Hypochlorite by continuous process. Commercially available sodium hypochlorite usually has a strength between 2 to 5.25% w/v. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small foot print (because of continuous and intensified reactor and short residence time) and environmental friendly.

Technology status:

The lab scale method has been tested for several hours. The efficacy of hypochlorite strength is also checked by controlled oxidation of alcohols. Technology is to be demonstrated at bench scale.

Publications: Sharma, Y.; Moolya, S. and Kulkarni, A. A. (2016) Continuous flow oxidation of alcohols using TEMPO and spot synthesized hypochlorite (*manuscript under preparation*)

Process for continuous nitration of Pendimethalin

Executive Summary

- A process for Pendimethalin synthesis based on di-nitration of substituted aniline is developed.
- Dinitroaniline derivatives are an important class of compounds with wide applications in herbicides and pesticides. For example, Pendimethalin is a widely-used selective herbicide in agricultural industry.
- In the industrial batch production of Pendimethalin in chlorinated solvent, the aniline solution is treated with dilute nitric acid as the first step. After separation of the organic phase and spent acid phase, the organic phase is treated with more concentrated nitric acid as the second step. Batch procedure produces mixture of isomers in different ratios based on the reaction parameters and duration of operation.
- The developed process is based on one step di-nitration employing concentrated nitric acid as nitrating agent and leads to higher selectivity towards Pendimethalin compared to other isomer.

Background

Dinitroaniline derivatives are generally produced by nitration of aniline derivatives. These nitration reactions are extremely hazardous due to highly exothermic thermodynamics as well as possible decomposition and explosion of nitro compounds. Also, selectivity is not satisfying due to easy oxidation or over-nitration of aniline derivatives and protection of the amino group by acetylation may be required prior to nitration. Developed process enables selective and continuous, one step dinitration procedure for dinitration of herbicide. Present route is much safer compared to conventional approach and utilizes very less amount of solvent.

Process description

The developed process uses concentrated nitric acid as nitrating agent (see reactions shown in the following) in a tubular reactor as well as in a CSTR with excellent mixing and heat transfer performance.

Conventional two-step di-nitration for Pendimethalin synthesis in the batch system

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at reaction temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Efficient heat transfer to avoid hot spots
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves more than 94% conversion with greater than 92% selectivity of di-nitro derivatives in a single step (batch procedure employ two steps). The by-product formation is also substantially less. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as small footprint, less solvent and no sulfuric acid.

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Scale-up approach is ready.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Continuous Flow Synthesis and Isolation of Quinaldines

Executive Summary

Continuous flow synthesis of 6-nitroquinaldine from 4-nitroaniline is demonstrated using sulfuric acid as a homogeneous catalyst. The extent of reaction was monitored for various parameters viz. temperature, residence time, mole ratio of sulfuric acid to substrate, mole ratio of crotonaldehyde to substrate, etc. For variety of reasons, tubular reactor was not found to be a suitable and beneficial system for conducting this reaction and hence CSTRs in series was used. The approach has been extended for continuous reactions of six different anilines and their results are compared with batch reactions.

Background

The Skraup procedure is a classical method for the synthesis of quinoline that involves use of a large amount of sulfuric acid at temperatures above 150°C, and the reaction is violent. Hence to make it feasible for the industrial scale the reaction is performed at 95°C.

Process description

The developed process uses sulphuric acid as catalyst (see reactions shown in the following) in a continuous stirred tank reactor.

R¹: H, R²: H, NO₂, R³: H, NO₂, CH₃, OCH₃

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The flow synthesis has an advantage over batch process in terms of yield improvement. Sulfuric acid acts as a homogeneous catalyst and the condition of optimum sulfuric acid concentration results in better yield of the desired product. Results indicate that the reactions performed at optimum sulfuric acid concentration with CSTR in series configuration helped to improve the yield of the product when compared with equal batch time. The modification from conventional batch isolation to continuous isolation of the product improves the efficiency of the process in terms of high throughput of the product and hence is the added intensification to the continuous flow synthesis.

Publications: Yadav, M; Kulkarni S. and Kulkarni A. A. (2016) Continuous flow synthesis of quinaldines, OPRD (manuscript submitted)

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for continuous flow synthesis of Silver nanoparticles

Executive Summary

- A process for continuous flow synthesis of silver nanoparticles based on citrate reduction route has been developed in a series of CSTRs assembly.
- The primary application of the synthesized silver nanoparticles is in antibacterial technology.
- The currently available methods for preparing silver nanoparticle suspensions are not designed towards large scale production. Kinetics and reaction conversion are unknown and costlier equipment and reagents are utilized.
- The current process is economical both from the raw material and equipment point of view. The average particle sizes can be varied from about 80 nm to 120 nm. The reaction kinetics have been derived and the process is designed for 100% conversion.

Background

Silver nanoparticles find applications in conductive inks, diagnostics and antibacterial applications. Most of the syntheses occur in a matter of minutes and are carried out in batch reactors. Thus the productivity can be significantly increased by switching to the continuous mode of operation.

Process description

The developed process uses trisodium citrate to reduce silver nitrate. The reaction is carried out at 90°C. Trisodium citrate also acts as the capping agent. Citrate capped silver nanoparticles are ideal for antibacterial applications.

The key process steps are:

- Passing a premixed solution of the reagents and costabilizer prepared at room temperature (reaction does not occur at room temperature) into an SS coil for quickly heating the reaction mixture upto 90°C (residence time of operation~ 1 min).
- Passing the heated reaction mixture into a series of isothermal jacketed CSTRs in series (90°C) with optimized volumes, volume ratios and order of arrangement where the nucleation and growth of AgNPs takes place(total residence time 40 min).
- The backmixing inside the assembly can be used to control the particle size from 80 to 120 nm. The backmixing can be tuned by varying the number of CSTRs, volume of CSTRs and the order of arrangement. Mole ratio and temperature are kept the same.
- For preparing smaller nanoparticles in the range of 5-10 nm, sodium borohydride is used as reducing agent with the rest of the process unchanged.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes: The process was designed for cost effective production of citrate capped AgNP suspensions. The method used a single phase, CSTRs in series approach, which introduced only the required extent of axial dispersion while also maintaining a low S/V ratio (which leads to significantly low deposition). The method of droplet flow suffers from low throughput higher pressure drops and is also hard to scale up.

Technology status: Laboratory scale process developed. The bench top reactor can synthesize 2 g/day of 80 nm particles and 36 g/day of 5-10 nm particles. Scale-up approach is ready.

Patents: Filed (NCL-INV-2015-59)

Publication: Deshpande, J. B. and Kulkarni, A. A. (2016) Reaction Kinetics and Reactor Design for Synthesis of Ag Nanoparticle by Citrate Reduction: Experiments and Scale-up Approach (**submitted**)

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

A Process for 4-methoxyphenol from hydroquinone

Executive Summary

- A laboratory scale process has been developed for 4-methoxyphenol (4 MP) from hydroquinone (HQ) using methanol as alkylating agent.
- Various catalysts were synthesized and screened for O-alkylation of hydroquinone reaction.
- The best catalyst was selected for further study and various reaction parameters such as reaction time, temperature, mole ratio, catalyst loading etc. have been optimized.

Background

- 4-methoxy phenol has many applications in manufacturing of dyes and pharmaceuticals. It is used as an inhibitor, a stabilizer to inhibit peroxide formation in ethers and as an inhibitor in vinyl and acrylic monomers. The global demand is around 20000 tpa, while India imports around 3000 tpa from China and Indonesia.
- Industrially 4-methoxyphenol is manufactured by using dimethyl sulphate as methylating agent which is extremely toxic. When Dimethyl carbonate is used as alkylating agent, there is formation of CO₂, difficulties in separation, in situ high pressure generation and need to use separately methanol as solvent. Mainly basic catalysts are used but as basicity increases, selectivity of dialkylated products also increases. Also basic catalyst leads to C-alkylation of hydroquinone.

Process description

- Methanol is better alkylating agent and solvent for the reaction than DMC and DMS. Desired temperature range for hydroquinone alkylation is 200-210°C.
- Ionic liquids are highly acidic in nature. Different types of ionic liquids have been prepared such as supported/ functionalized/ immobilized on silica gel, cellulose and L-proline and used to catalyse o-alkylation of HQ in the presence of excess methanol. Since supported IL's are heterogeneous, there is no separation issue and reusability of catalyst is possible.
- A continuous tubular reactor set-up is being developed for further experimentation.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Methanol was used as both solvent and methylating agent.
- Heterogeneous acid catalyst can be easily separated and reuse.
- Methanol can be recycled and reused for reactions.
- Simple separation protocol by distillation and steam stripping
- Clean process technology

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Validation of reactor operation on pilot scale needs to be done Exploring industry partner for setting up a demonstration plant.

Patents:

Filed disclosure/ patents on catalyst system (one pot process for synthesis of alkyl aryl ether compounds using supported ionic liquid catalysts)

Publications:

In preparation. (Selective o-alkylation of hydroquinone using methanol over acidic catalyst)

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

A Process for Diethyl Phthalate

Executive Summary

- A laboratory scale process has been developed for Diethyl Phthalate (DEP) using Ionic liquid based catalyst system.
- Various catalysts ionic liquid based as well as solid acids were synthesized and screened for esterification reaction.
- The best catalyst was selected for further study and various reaction parameters such as reaction time, temperature, mole ratio, catalyst loading etc. have been optimized.

Background

- Diethyl phthalate (DEP) is a phthalate ester, often used to bind cosmetics and fragrances. Other industrial uses include plasticizers, detergent bases and aerosol sprays.
- Phthalate esters such as dimethyl phthalate (DMP), dibutyl phthalate (DBP) and dioctyl phthalate (DOP) are the most important plasticizers for polymers and these can be prepared by treating methanol, n-butanol, or 2-ethylhexanol, respectively with phthalic anhydride in the liquid phase either with a monoester intermediate stage or by a direct route.
- Phthalate esters constitute more than 70% of the plasticizer market in the world. These are mainly used in the polymerization of olefins especially vinyl chloride (PVC), ethylene, and propylene.
- Mineral liquid acids, such as sulphuric acid and p-toluenesulphonic acid are widely used in industrial esterification reactions, owing to their low price and high activity. However the drawbacks they suffered are obvious, such as their corrosive nature, the occurrence of side reactions, and the difficulty for the separation of the catalyst from the reaction mixture.

Process description

- Esterification of phthalic anhydride with ethanol using Bronsted acidic ILs as has several advantages such as high conversion rate and selectivity.
- Ionic liquids are highly acidic in nature. Different types of ionic liquids have been prepared such as supported/ functionalized/ immobilized on silica gel, cellulose and L-proline and used to catalyse esterification reaction in the presence of excess alcohol. Since supported IL's are heterogeneous, there is no separation issue and reusability of catalyst is possible.
- A continuous tubular reactor set-up is being developed for further experimentation.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- High conversion (90-95 %) of phthalic anhydride and high selectivity (95%) of diethyl phthalate over IL-2 catalyst can be achieved at moderate reaction conditions.
- IL based catalyst or Heterogeneous acid catalyst can be easily separated and recycled.
- Clean process technology

Technology status:

- Laboratory scale batch process developed.
- Validation of reactor operation on pilot scale needs to be done
- Exploring industry partner for setting up a demonstration plant.

Publications:

In preparation. (An efficient, stable and reusable ionic liquid as a catalyst for Esterification of phthalic anhydride with ethanol)

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

A Process for 3 Methyl Pentenone (MPO)

Executive Summary

- A laboratory scale process has been developed for 3 Methyl Pentenone (MPO)
- Various catalysts homogeneous as well as well as heterogeneous basic catalysts were synthesized and screened for aldol condensation reaction.
- The best catalyst was selected for further study and various reaction parameters such as reaction time, temperature, mole ratio, catalyst loading etc. have been optimized.

Background

- 3 Methyl Pentenone (MPO) is an important ketone mainly used in fine and aroma chemicals.
- MPO can be made by aldol condensation of acetaldehyde and methyl ethyl ketone. Aldol condensation is a very important reaction and has been used in large scale production of several commodity chemicals.
- Conventionally, Aldol condensation is carried out using sodium hydroxide or sulfuric acid in a homogeneous phase. The use of such homogeneous catalysts has numerous disadvantages such as waste production, corrosion and catalyst recovery and also adds to the processing cost due to issues in the isolation of the final products.
- There are several reports concerning the use of heterogeneous acids and bases as catalyst for such type of reactions. Solid catalysts have a number of advantages over the conventional homogeneous systems. The heterogeneous catalyst can be recycled back avoiding the use of mineral acid and eliminating the processing issues involved with it. The advantages of heterogeneous catalyst are well known and are being well practiced.

Process description

- Aldol condensation of acetaldehyde and methyl ethyl ketone in presence of solid acid catalyst under controlled conditions leads to MPO.
- Aldol condensation takes place in three steps i.e. enolate formation, reaction of acetaldehyde with the enolate to form an alcoholic product, and dehydration to give a α , β -unsaturated product.

- A continuous tubular reactor set-up needs to be developed for further experimentation.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- 100% conversion of acetaldehyde and high selectivity (70-85%) to MPO can be achieved by properly manipulating the reaction conditions.
- Heterogeneous acid catalyst can be easily separated and recycled.
- Clean process technology

Technology status:

- Laboratory scale batch process developed.
- Validation of reactor operation on pilot scale needs to be done.
- Exploring industry partner for setting up a demonstration plant.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

A continuous process for Pentaerythritol

Executive Summary

- A laboratory scale continuous process for aldol condensation of acetaldehyde and formaldehyde followed by Cannizzaro reaction to Pentaerythritol has been developed.
- A reaction protocol has been developed which gives high selectivity to pentaerythritol.

Background

- The pentaerythritol finds applications in lubricants, fire-retardant compositions, adhesives, and other formulations where the cross-linking capabilities are of critical importance.
- Pentaerythritol is produced in a variety of grades having differing amounts of dipentaerythritol and small quantities of linear formal.
- It is desirable to have a reaction protocol leading to better quality and in high yields.

Process description

The developed process employs intensified tubular reactor leading better process control.

- Pentaerythritol is produced by reaction of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde in the presence of a basic catalyst, generally an alkali or alkaline earth hydroxide. Reaction proceeds by aldol condensation, addition to the carbon adjacent to the hydroxyl on the acetaldehyde. The pentaerythrose so produced is converted to pentaerythritol by a crossed Cannizzaro reaction using formaldehyde.
- All the reaction steps are reversible except the last; this also leads to occurrence of other parallel reactions resulting into formation of various impurities. Generally mild reaction conditions are favored for optimum results. However, formation of by-products cannot be entirely eliminated, particularly dipentaerythritol and the linear formal of pentaerythritol.
- Operating parameters like temperature, residence time and mole ratio plays an important role in conversion and selectivity.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- The selectivity of pentaerythritol can be manipulated depending the product specification by changing the reaction conditions.
- High purity pentaerythritol can be produced for special applications.
- Acetaldehyde and formaldehyde conversion is 90-100 %,
- The developed process has following advantages over conventional process.
 - Intensified process and better process control
 - Gives better selectivity and higher yield of desired isomer
 - Low cost of production, consistent product quality and generation of less waste

Technology status:

- Proof-of-concept has been established at laboratory scale in a continuous mode.
- Needs further investigation on pilot scale to establish raw material consumption and generate design data.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

A continuous process for m-cresol

Executive Summary

- A laboratory scale continuous process for diazotization and hydrolysis of m-toluidine has been developed.
- The various reaction parameters such as residence time, temperature, mole ratio, etc. have been optimized.
- A continuous pilot plant has been developed and being investigated at collaborator's site.

Background

- m-cresol is an intermediate used in manufacture of a variety of products such as antioxidants, disinfectants, dyestuffs, optical brighteners, pesticides, drugs, flavors and fragrances.
- Diazotization of m-toluidine followed by hydrolysis is practiced for the production of m-Cresol.
- Due to high exothermicity of the reaction undesired isomers are formed and may also lead to runaway of the reaction making it very unsafe.
- The partial conversion leads to separation issues and also the desired purity of the m-cresol. The process in a batch mode also adds to energy cost and needs higher capital investment.

Process description

We have developed an intensified continuous process for m-cresol in a tubular reactor.

- The diazotization of m-toluidine is carried out in a tubular reactor by feeding the m-toluidine solution and nitrosation reagent in the desired mole ratio and at an appropriate flow rate and reaction temperature so as to achieve complete conversion to diazonium salt. The product stream is further heated in second stage of the continuous reactor to undergo hydrolysis resulting into the formation of m-cresol.
- Operating parameters like temperature, residence time and mole ratio play an important role in conversion and selectivity.
- As the process is a continuous, it can be operated very safely and also reduces the energy requirement.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- m-toluidine conversion is almost 100%, while m-cresol of 100% purity can be isolated.
- Easy isolation of the product from the reaction mixture.
- A continuous intensified and safe process resulting into consistent product quality.

Technology status:

- Laboratory scale process developed.
- A pilot scale continuous reaction set-up has been developed for further experimentation.
- Validation of process parameters on pilot scale needs to be done to establish the Techno-economic feasibility as Raw material costing appears favorable.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

A continuous process for 1-Nitro Naphthalene

Executive Summary

- A laboratory scale continuous process for nitration of naphthalene developed.
- The various reaction parameters such as residence time, temperature, mole ratio, etc. have been optimized.
- A continuous pilot plant has been developed and being investigated at collaborator's site.

Background

- 1-Nitro naphthalene is widely used in manufacturing of variety of dyes, drugs, perfumes, rubber chemicals, tanning agents, fungicides and pesticides.
- Conventionally, nitration is carried out by using mixed acid such as nitric acid and sulfuric acid, which results into generation of large amount of acid waste.
- Due to high exothermicity of the reaction undesired isomers are formed and may also leads to runaway of the reaction making it very unsafe.
- The partial conversion leads to separation issues and also the desired purity of the 1 - nitro naphthalene isomer. The nitration operation in a batch mode also adds to energy cost and needs higher capital investment.

Process description

- We have developed a more efficient continuous process for nitration of naphthalene and use of sulfuric acid has been successfully avoided. As the process is a continuous, can be operated very safely and also reduces the energy requirement.

- The nitration of naphthalene is carried out in a tubular reactor by feeding the nitric acid and naphthalene solution in solvent in the desired mole ratio and at an appropriate flow rate and reaction temperature so as achieve complete conversion of naphthalene. The product stream is cooled to room and separated into two layers.
- The crude nitro naphthalene obtained can be crystallized to get the 1-nitronaphthalene having purity more than 99.5%.
- Operating parameters like temperature, pressure, time and mole ratio plays an important role in conversion and selectivity.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- The selectivity of 1- nitro isomer is around 95-98% on using the developed reaction protocol.
- Naphthalene conversion is almost 100 %.
- Easy isolation of the product from the reaction mixture.
- A continuous intensified and safe process resulting into consistent product quality.

Technology status:

- Laboratory scale process developed.
- A pilot scale continuous reaction set-up has been developed for further experimentation.
- Validation of process parameters on pilot scale needs to be done to establish the Techno-economic feasibility as Raw material costing appears favorable.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Coumarin Derivatives from Phenolic Acetates and Acrylates

Executive Summary

- A process for coumarin derivatives based on C-H activation of phenolic acetates and acrylates is developed.
- Coumarin derivatives find application in natural products widely found in plants and exhibit excellent biological and pharmacological activity including antitumor, anti-HIV, anticoagulation, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant. In addition, they are also widely used as food additives, as optical brightening agents, light-emitting diodes, as fluorescent probes, and laser dyes.
- The conventional process using the most common approach to their synthesis is undoubtedly the Pechmann condensation and its related reactions.
- The developed method is based on Rh-catalyzed ortho C-H bond activation of phenolic acetates with acrylates in the presence of NaOAc as base and HCO₂H as reducing agent that produces synthetically useful coumarin derivatives.

Background

Previous classical methods employ stoichiometric quantities of strong Lewis or Brønsted acids, often leading to mixtures of regioisomers. To overcome these difficulties we wish to report a method for the synthesis of industrially important coumarin chemical. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional processes.

Process description

The developed process uses C-H activation of phenolic acetates and acrylates using rhodium as catalyst (see reactions shown in the following) in a round bottom flask.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate, reagent and catalyst at room temperature.
- Heated the reaction at 100 °C for 3-12 hr depending on substrate used.
- Mole ratio of catalyst and additive to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal parameters for enhancing selectivity towards coumarin have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- The process achieves more than 80% conversion with greater than 96% selectivity of coumarin derivatives (compared to ~80% with the conventional process).
- The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as formation of one isomer.

Technology status: Laboratory scale method developed.

Patents: Patent Application Indian filing- INV-2015-73

Publications: Sunita K. Gadakh, Soumen Dey, and Sudalai A. (2015), *J. Org. Chem.*, **80**, 11544

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Oxidative esterification of aldehydes with alkylarenes or alcohols

Executive Summary

- A lab process for Benzyl or alkyl esters based on esterification of aldehydes with alkylarenes or alcohols is developed based on Ti-superoxide catalysts
- Benzyl or alkyl esters finds application as versatile 'building blocks' in the synthesis of fine chemicals, natural products, polymeric materials, etc.
- The traditional esterification processes involve a two-step procedure of stoichiometric activation of a carboxylic acid as an anhydride, acyl halide or activated ester followed by subsequent nucleophilic substitution with alcohols.

Background

A metal-free methodology for the synthesis of benzyl esters has been developed via oxidative C–O bond formation. However, these approaches suffer from narrow substrate scope, use of stoichiometric amounts of toxic and hazardous heavy metal oxidants, dry reaction conditions, longer reaction time, poor yields as well as low reaction efficiency.

Process description

The developed process uses Ti-superoxide catalyzed for the direct conversion of aldehydes into carboxylic esters via direct C–H activation of alkylarenes or using alcohols.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- The process achieves more than 95.5% conversion with greater than 96% selectivity. Maximum yield of the product in both the cases are around 80 -90 %.
- Various substrates were screened to see the application of this process. Interestingly, this protocol is quite successful on a large scale production of dioctyl phthalate, a plasticizer in the polymer industry, with excellent yields (96%) in the 100 g scale.
- The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as simple reaction steps without using any toxic chemical.
- The development of a single-step oxidative esterification of aldehydes under truly heterogeneous catalytic conditions that minimize hazardous wastes is highly desirable from both economic and environmental points of view.

Technology status: Laboratory scale process has been developed.

Publications: Soumen Dey, Sunita K. Gadakh and A. Sudalai* (2015), *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 13, 10631

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Catalytic process for the synthesis of Tertiary butyl phenol (TBP)

Executive Summary

- An eco-friendly catalytic process has been developed for the synthesis of TBP where phosphorus pent oxide (P₂O₅) is used as a catalyst for the reaction.
- TBP is prepared by Friedel–Crafts alkylation of phenol with tertiary butyl alcohol (TBA)
- For isolation of reaction products a viable, simple extraction method has been established.
- The developed process leads to higher selectivity towards para-TBP.

Background

Tertiary butyl phenol (TBP) has an important industrial application. Alkylation reaction of phenol with tert-butyl alcohol (TBA) is an important reaction both in organic synthesis and chemical manufacturing. The alkylated phenol products are used as raw materials for the manufacture of a variety of resins, durable surface coatings, varnishes, wire enamels, printing inks, surface-active agents, rubber chemicals, antioxidants, fungicides, petroleum additives, ultraviolet absorbers, and heat stabilizers for polymeric materials.

Process description

The developed process uses phenol and tertiary butyl alcohol as starting raw material using acidic catalyst (see reactions shown in the following) in an autoclave reactor.

The key process steps are:

- Autoclave was charged with various amounts of phenol and TBA. The reaction solution was stirred at 300 rpm and subsequently solution was heated at temperature 230 °C & 65 bars pressure for 6-8 hrs.
- Organic layer is easily separated by simple extraction process.
- Optimal process parameters for production of TBP have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- A process for synthesis of tertiary butyl phenol (TBP) has been developed.
- The main advantages of the process are i) an eco-friendly and ii) the overall cost process is very low as compared to other conventional process.

Technology status:

- Bench scale process has been developed for the synthesis of TBP.

Patents:

Kamble, Sanjay Pandurag; Sudalai, Arumugam, A novel process for the preparation of tertiary butyl phenols, patent discourse #2016-INV-19.

Synthesis of quinoline carboxylates from arylamines

Executive Summary

- A process for quinoline carboxylates based on C–H bond activation of arylamines is developed.
- Quinoline carboxylates are ubiquitous heterocyclic units found extensively in many natural products and pharmaceuticals.
- The conventional process transition metal-catalyzed functionalization of a variety of less active C–H bonds has received substantial importance in the construction of heterocyclic scaffolds. In particular, Rh(III), Ru(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II) metal complexes have provided exciting opportunities for the efficient synthesis of condensed heterocycles via chelation-assisted directing group C–H bond functionalization.
- The developed process is based only on rhodium catalyzed annulation of anilines with alkynic esters allowing for the high-yield synthesis of quinoline carboxylates with excellent regioselectivity is described.

Background

Most of the methods suffer from limited availability of substrates, complicated multi-step procedures and low regioselectivity, leading to low yields of products. The process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process.

Process description

The developed process uses rhodium catalyst for C-H activation (see reactions shown in the following) in a round bottom flask.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of substrate and nitrating agent at low temperature.
- Use appropriate flow rates to achieve the desired residence time in the flow reactor
- Mole ratio of nitrating agent to substrate is the key to get maximum yield of the desired isomer. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 4 NOX have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- The process achieves more than 90.5% conversion with greater than 95% selectivity of quinoline derivatives (compared to ~80% with the conventional process). The by-product formation is also substantially less in the developed process.
- Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as simple reaction step and high regioselectivity.

Technology status: Laboratory scale process developed for synthesis of quinoline carboxylates.

Patents: Patent Application IN/1700/DEL/2004

Publications: Sunita K. Gadakh, S. Dey and A. Sudalai. (2016), *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 14, 2969–2977

Propyl Acetate by catalytic reactive distillation

Executive Summary

- Catalytic reactive distillation process has been developed for the synthesis of propyl acetate where amberlyst-15 used as a catalyst for the reaction.
- Propyl Acetate obtained in the laboratory scale process shows conversion above 99.5% and 99.9% purity.
- The side reactions of etherification and dehydration can be almost completely suppressed using, cation-exchange resin, Amberlyst-15.
- More cost effective and eco-friendly process compare to the present industrial processes. Hexane is used as a solvent as well as entrainer to increase the purity of product.

Background

There is an increasing the inclination of chemical industries toward new processes that should meet the requirement such as generation of nearly zero waste chemicals, less energy, and sufficient uses of product chemicals in various application. Hence, the esterification is widely employed reaction in the organic process industry. The reaction is carried out between carboxylic acid and alcohol at with or without the present of the different catalyst under such specific conditions. Propyl acetate is used as solvents in paints, adhesives and organic media instead of aromatic compounds.

Process description

The developed process uses acetic acid and 1-Propanol as starting raw material where Amberlyst-15 is used as a catalyst along with hexane as entrainer/solvent (see reactions shown in the following).

The key process steps are:

- Reactive-distillation concept was employed for synthesis of propyl acetate.
- An eco-friendly, cost effective, catalytic reactive distillation process for the synthesis of propyl acetate has been developed wherein the colourless and characteristics odour product with more than 99.9% pure and > 99.5% yields is achieved.
- Optimal process parameters for production of propyl acetate have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- A catalytic reactive distillation approach was employed for synthesis of propyl acetate has been developed from readily available raw materials such as acetic acid and 1-propanol and using an amberlyst-15 catalyst.

The main advantages of the process are i) an eco-friendly and ii) the overall cost process is very low as compared conventional process iii) colorless and characteristics odour product is obtained iv) the side reactions of etherification and dehydration can be almost completely suppressed.

Technology status: Batch scale process has been developed for propyl acetate with purity >99.5%

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Autocatalytic process for the synthesis of tributyl citrate

Executive Summary

- An eco-friendly autocatalytic process is developed for the synthesis of TBC where citric acid used as a catalyst for the reaction.
- TBC obtained in the laboratory scale process shows 95-99.9% purity and colorless product
- The advantage of autocatalytic reaction is the absence of separation step and regeneration of catalyst. Further, the overall cost of the process is low as compared to heterogenous catalyst.

Background

Organic esters are important intermediates in chemical and pharmaceutical industries. Tri-ethyl citrate (TEC) and tri-n-butyl citrate (TBC) are used as nontoxic plasticizers in toys, medical products, printing ink coatings, cosmetics, and other applications. Citric acid can be esterified with alcohols like ethanol and n-butanol through a series of reactions to yield TEC and TBC. The catalysts used in traditional synthesis process were mainly sulfuric acid, titanate, solid acid etc. But this process have some disadvantages such as equipment corrosion, more byproducts, tedious workup procedure and environmental problem, higher cost, difficult separation from products and more consumption of energy. The global plasticizers market has registered revenue of USD 26 billion in 2009 and it was projected that the global annual demand for the plasticizers market may exceed more than 13.2 million tonnes per year till 2018.

Process description

The developed process uses citric acid and butanol as starting raw material where acidity of citric acid was used to enhance the rate of reaction.

The key process steps are:

- Reaction distillation concept was employed for synthesis of TBC.
- An eco-friendly, cost effective, auto-catalyzed process for synthesis of butyl citrate has been developed wherein the colourless product with more than 95% pure and > 85% yields is achieved.
- Mole ratio of reactants as well as reaction temperature is important parameters which will give colorless and better quality of the desired product i.e. TBC. Optimal process parameters for production of TBC have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- A reactive distillation approach was employed for synthesis of TBC has been developed from readily available raw materials such as citric acid and butanol and using auto-catalyst.
- The main advantages of the process are i) an eco-friendly and ii) the overall cost process is very low as compared conventional process iii) Absence of separation step and no need of catalyst recovered & recycled iv) colorless product is obtained.

Technology status: Bench scale process is developed for the synthesis of TBC with purity >99.5%

Patents: Kamble Sanjay Pandurang, Autocatalytic process for the preparation of tri butyl citrate using reactive distillation method, Indian Patent application #3744/DEL/2015.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for synthesis of *p*-Methoxyacetophenone (4-MAP)

Executive Summary

- A cost effective, eco-friendly process for synthesis of 4-MAP has been developed
- Conventional 4-MAP was produced by Friedel–Crafts reactions, with acid chlorides or anhydrides, and these processes produce significant amounts of corrosive vapor and aqueous aluminum waste.
- The developed process is based on solid catalyst that leads to higher selectivity towards 4-MAP compared to 2-MAP.

Background

Acetanisole is an aromatic compound with an aroma described as sweet, fruity, nutty, and similar to vanilla. 4'-Methoxyacetophenone (4-MAP) is used as a component of perfumes and as a chemical intermediate in the manufacture of pharmaceuticals, resins, and flavouring agents. Conventional 4-MAP was produced by Friedel–Crafts reactions, with acid chlorides or anhydrides, often require excess quantities of Lewis acid (i.e., AlCl₃), and they can produce significant amounts of corrosive vapor and aqueous aluminum waste.

Process description

The developed process uses acetic acid and anisole as starting raw material using solid catalyst (see reactions shown in the following) in a typical stirred reactor.

The key process steps are:

- Mixing of reactants, solvent and addition of catalyst in stepwise at temperature 80 °C.
- Mole ratio of reactants as well as solvent to reactant is the key to get maximum yield of the desired product i.e. 4-MAP. Optimal process parameters for enhancing selectivity towards 4-MAP have been established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- A process for synthesis of 4-methoxyacetophenone has been developed from readily available raw materials such as anisole and acetic acid and using new catalyst.
- The main advantages of the process are i) an eco-friendly and ii) the overall cost process is very low as compared to conventional process.
- The optimum process conditions for synthesis of 4-methoxyacetophenone have been established.

Technology status:

- Process demonstration for the synthesis of 4-MAP with purity >99.2% was given to Ms. Hari OM Chemicals, Bhavnagar, Gujarat at pilot scale 20 kg/batch at client site.

Patents: A new process for the preparation of aromatic ketones from arenes, Indian Patent application # 0416/DEL/2015

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Biocoagulants and Intensified Coagulation for Water Treatment

Executive Summary

- Newer biocoagulants and biocoagulant formulations have been developed for effective treatment of industrial wastewaters.
- The developed biocoagulants can effectively reduce COD/ colour from effluents.
- The developed methodology can offer new GREEN approach to effluent treatment
- Intensification in the form of coagulation + Cavitation can further improve the process.

Background

Coagulation is one of the most widely used methodology in industrial wastewater treatment and any incremental improvement in this can substantially reduce load on the subsequent treatment processes thereby improving process economics; overall reduction in treatment cost. Use of biocoagulants can provide new alternative to existing chemical coagulants and ease of availability.

Process description

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

Newer biocoagulants such as *Acanthocereus tetragonus* as biocoagulant have been developed for application in dye wastewater treatment. The biocoagulant are effective in reduction in color and exhibit wide operating pH. Though coagulant dose of the biocoagulant is higher as compared to the chemical coagulant, the sludge volume is comparatively less. Intensification using cavitation improves process. The present research provides applications of biocoagulants as an alternative in treatment of textile dye wastewater effluent.

Technology status: Laboratory scale process developed.

Publications: Chethana M., Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, S.Raja, Vivek V. Ranade. 2015. Application of Biocoagulant *Acanthocereus tetragonus* (Triangle cactus) in Dye wastewater Treatment. *Journal of Environ. Res. Dev.* Vol. 9 No. 3A, 813-821.

Kavita Prajapati, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, Deepak J. Killedar and V. V. Ranade, "Differentiating process performance of various coagulants in removal of Congo Red and Orange G dyes", *International Journal of Chemical Reactor Engineering*. Vol. 14 (1), 195–211, DOI: [10.1515/ijcre-2015-0083](https://doi.org/10.1515/ijcre-2015-0083), (2016)

Chethana M., Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, S. Raja and Vivek V. Ranade. 2016. Green approach to Dye Wastewater Treatment using Biocoagulants. Submitted.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Activated carbons & process for removing pollutants

Executive Summary

- A new adsorbent –activated carbon from *Cassia fistula* has been developed.
- The developed adsorbent is superior to many commercial activated carbons.
- The new adsorbent is found to be useful in wastewater treatment applications.
- The new adsorbent is found to be effective in desulfurization of fuels and organics.

Background

Development of newer adsorbent materials that have selectivity, increased capacity and better properties for the removal of organics is critical to both process separations and effluent treatment. India lags far behind in terms of development of new materials such as adsorbents/membranes etc. and hence research in this important area is most crucial.

Process description

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

A single raw material- *Cassia fistula*, can be used to tailor-make adsorbents in such a way that the developed materials have different porosity and surface area. CFP-450 has a maximum surface area ~ 1100 m²/g and excellent adsorption properties. Phosphoric acid-modified forms of CF have high sulfur removal capacity. CFP-450 has excellent dye removal characteristics and has a wide range of operating pH - 2 to 9. Near total dye removal can be obtained using CFP-450 and CFP-900. The developed adsorbents have good potential in industrial wastewater treatment and compare well or even better than some of the important and widely used commercial adsorbents.

Technology status: Laboratory scale process developed. Two applications are developed.

Patents: Ranade V. V., Bhandari V. M. and Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam. 2014. A process for removing pollutants/chemicals from aqueous as well as organic streams using *Cassia fistula* (Golden shower). Patent Filed (0231-NF-2014 : 2014-INV-0088).

Publications: Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, Monal S. Salvi, Saijal Jain, Snehal D. Hadawale, and Vivek V. Ranade, Development of Newer Adsorbents: Activated Carbons Derived from Carbonized *Cassia fistula*. Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. (2015). (DOI: 10.1021/acs.iecr.5b02945).

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process Development - Polyaluminum chloride

Executive Summary

- Process development for inorganic coagulant-Polyaluminum chloride with specific basicity and molecular weight for increased effectiveness.
- Methodology for making effective inorganic polymers such as PAC, PAS as coagulants.
- Development of coagulant formulations.

Background

Use of inorganic polymers such as poly aluminum chloride as a coagulant is increasing due to its effectiveness in water and wastewater treatment. However, cost considerations along with stability of the product are the major considerations apart from improving the process performance. Thus, newer products and processes will help industry, in particular and society, in general.

Process description

Aluminum/aluminum chloride/aluminum hydroxide + HCl \longrightarrow Polyaluminum chloride

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

Poly aluminium Chloride (PAC) is an inorganic polymer, a partially neutralized hydrate having the formula- $Al_2Cl_6-x(OH)x.6H_2O$ (where $x = 1.5$) and is widely used in chemical industry and water treatment applications. Issues in PAC Technology include:

- Stability of the PAC – Higher stability required
- Molecular weight of the PAC product – No clear Guidelines
- Basicity of PAC product and different product characteristics.

The PAC obtained using Aluminum/Aluminum chloride and HCl was found to have molecular weight of ~1000 Da and OH/Al ratio of ~2.5-6. The products were effective in dye wastewater treatment. Newer modifications such as PAS or PASiC are being explored. The development of technology for PAC, especially using low cost byproducts of existing unit, can be an attractive option that can be useful for various applications in process separations and in wastewater treatment apart from utilizing existing waste such as dilute HCl or aluminium chloride.

Technology status: Laboratory scale process is being developed.

Publications:

Snehal D. Hadawale, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, Sunil S. Joshi and Vivek V. Ranade., "Synthesis, Characterization and Application of Polyaluminum Chloride Coagulant: Treatment of Dye Wastewater", Presented at National Conference on Frontiers in Chemical and Material Sciences- FCMS-2015, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Jan 16-17, 2015.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Vortex diodes as effluent treatment devices

Executive Summary

- A new hydrodynamic cavitation process using vortex diode has been developed for Industrial wastewater treatment.
- Process is useful for treating different industrial effluents e.g. dye, distillery wastewaters.
- A very high reduction in COD and ammoniacal nitrogen could be achieved.

Background

India faces a huge challenge in terms of effluent treatment, water recycle and reuse for protection of environment and for avoiding water scarcity (~200 million m³ untreated wastewater/year in India alone). Stricter pollution control norms demand Indian Industry to apply newer methods of treatment that are techno-economic and efficient.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process can remove COD, ammoniacal nitrogen and/or color to the extent of 80-90%. The process is simple to operate and is cost-effective alternative to existing effluent treatment methods. The technology can be implemented alone or in combination with other processes. Batch process or continuous process. Successful trials at 1m³/h pilot plant scale.

Technology status: Pilot plant scale process developed and demonstrated. Technology Licensed to VIVIRA.

Patents: Ranade V. V., Kulkarni A. A., Bhandari V. M. 2013. Vortex diodes as effluent treatment devices, PCT Int. Appl. (2013) WO 2013054362 A2 20130418.

Ranade V. V. and Bhandari V. M. 2014. Patent Filed (0166NF2014 - 2179US046).

Publications: R. S. Hiremath, V. M. Bhandari and V. V. Ranade. Proc. AIChE Annual Meeting USA. (2013)
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 R. Saravanane, V. V. Ranade, V. M. Bhandari and A. Seshagiri Rao, "Urban Wastewater Treatment For Recycle And Reuse In Industrial Applications – Indian Scenario", in Ranade and Bhandari Eds. "Industrial wastewater treatment, recycling and reuse", Elsevier, UK, 2014.
 V. V. Ranade and V. M. Bhandari, "Industrial Wastewater Treatment, Recycle and Reuse-Past, Present and Future", in "Industrial wastewater treatment, recycling and reuse", Elsevier, UK, 2014.
 Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari and Vivek V. Ranade. J. Environ. Res. Dev., V8, 697, (2014).
 V. M. Bhandari, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam and V. V. Ranade, Chemical Industry Digest, 27, 82-86, (2014)
 V. M. Bhandari, LaxmiGayatri Sorokhaibam, V. V. Ranade, Proc. International Conference– Industrial waste and wastewater treatment and valorisation; IWWATV 2015, Athens, Greece 21-23 May, 2015 (2015).
 V. M. Bhandari, LaxmiGayatri Sorokhaibam and V.V. Ranade. Proc. XI Joint Convention STAI/DSTA, (2015).

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Spherical Activated Carbon from Resins

Executive Summary

- Newer adsorbents in the form of spherical activated carbon have been prepared using polymeric resins.
- The developed spherical activated carbons compare well with those available commercially.
- The newer materials, as such or in specifically modified form, could be highly useful as adsorbents.

Background

Development of newer adsorbent materials that have selectivity, increased capacity and better properties for the removal of organics is critical to both process separations and effluent treatment. India lags far behind in terms of development of new materials such as adsorbents/membranes etc. and hence research in this important area is most crucial.

Process description

Original Resins

Thermal/chemical
treatment

NCL-SAC-1

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

We have prepared spherical activated carbon using polymeric resins. The crucial aspect in the synthesis is controlled thermal treatment and environment/pre- or post-treatment that enable formation of well defined pore structure and gives high surface area. The surface area observed with the spherical activated carbon is of the order of 1000 m²/g. The characteristics of developed spherical activated carbons are excellent.

Iodine Number:	Commercial SAC	NCL-SAC-2
Using X/M formula	804.0	904.5
Using I _n Formula	934.7	1034.6

The development of spherical activated carbons, especially using polymeric resin waste can be an attractive option that can be useful for various applications in process separations and in wastewater treatment apart from utilizing existing waste.

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. Product is demonstrated to have properties comparable to commercial materials.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Process for synthesis of diphenyl methane (DPM)

Executive Summary

- A process for the synthesis of diphenyl methane (DPM) from benzyl chloride and benzene is under development.
- Diphenylmethane is an important chemical with applications in pharmaceutical and fine chemical industry
- The benzylation reactions are commercially carried out, using conventional homogeneous acid catalysts, such as anhydrous AlCl_3 . These processes generate a high volume of waste material.
- The catalyst developed is highly active with selectivity to DPM in a range of 65-75%. Catalyst is stable and can be recycled for 4-5 times without drop in activity.

Background : DPM is exported to various countries and the estimated present capacity is ~ 300 TPA. The process under development has key advantages of significantly reduced waste formation.

Process description : The developed process uses zinc ferrite as recyclable catalyst for the synthesis of DPM from benzene and benzyl chloride. The stoichiometric reaction is as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of DPM from benzene and benzyl chloride

The key features are:

- Work carried out on 20 ml reaction scale in a batch process.
- Mole ratio of benzyl chloride:benzene is key in achieving high selectivity to DPM and reducing the formation of side products.
- Induction period observed in the fresh reaction has been eliminated in the recycle experiments.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves 99% conversion with ~65-75% selectivity of DPM. DPM is reactive and undergoes benzylation easily resulting erosion in selectivity. Mole ratio of benzyl chloride:benzene is important parameter in governing selectivity to DPM. Reaction has long induction period and once the reaction is initiated progress of reaction is fast. Careful washing of the used catalyst avoiding contact with air results in complete elimination of induction period maintaining similar selectivity to DPM. This has resulted in significantly improving performance of the catalyst and intensifying the process.

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process development is in progress. Catalyst was recycled five times and reactivation of the catalyst led to original activity. Further recycle experiments also showed that the induction period was completely eliminated. Same performance was observed when the experiment was carried out at 80 ml scale. Further work on process intensification is in progress.

Patents: Patent application has been submitted to Patent office at NCL.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde to cinnamyl alcohol

Executive Summary

- A process for the hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde (CAL) to cinnamyl alcohol (COL) is developed
- Cinnamyl alcohol is used in fragrance industry, production of photosensitive polymers, the creation of inks for multicolor printing, the formulation of animal repellent compositions, and the development of effective insect attractants.
- Commercially cinnamyl alcohol is synthesized by a well known process called Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley (MPV) reduction using aluminium isopropoxide as a reagent. Major problem of the MPV reduction is disposal of large quantities of aluminum salts generated.
- The aim of this work was to optimize reaction conditions to achieve high conversion of CAL in shorter reaction time retaining high selectivity to COL.

Background

In India Cinnamyl alcohol is exclusively produced by MPV route. The present process is catalytic with the use of hydrogen gas for hydrogenation.

Process description

The hydrogenation of CAL was investigated in a high pressure Parr autoclave using 5%Pt/C catalyst and iso-propyl alcohol as solvent.

Hydrogenation of CAL is a complex hydrogenation reaction and leads to various hydrogenation products as shown in Figure. Optimization of reaction conditions was carried out to achieve high selectivity to COL with high conversion of CAL in shorter reaction time.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process is atom efficient without generation of any salt. Challenge is in achieving high selectivity to COL with high conversion of CAL. Catalyst deactivation is observed after 2 recycles. There is a need to investigate catalyst deactivation process and improve life of the catalyst.

Technology status:

Work on the intensification of the process has been carried out and >90% conversion of cinnamaldehyde has been achieved with >85% selectivity to cinnamyl alcohol in short reaction time of 30 minutes with 5% Pt/C as a catalyst and isopropyl alcohol as a solvent at 40°C temperature. The contact time was found to be important parameter in achieving high selectivity to COL. Catalyst could be recycled two times with slight drop in CAL conversion with IPA as a solvent. Further work on improving life of the catalyst is in progress.

Publications: Garkhedkar, A.M, Shingote, S.K., Rane, V.H., Kelkar, A.A. and Ranade, V.V. (2015), *Indian Chemical Engineer*, 1-21

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Synthesis of methyl phenyl carbamate

Executive Summary

- A process for the methoxycarbonylation of aniline to methyl phenyl carbamate (MPC) is developed
- Aromatic carbamates serve as isocyanate precursors and are valuable intermediates in the synthesis of pesticides, fungicides, herbicides, pharmaceuticals and polyurethane foams.
- Commercially carbamates have been synthesized using phosgene. There is a need to develop safer route because of highly toxic nature of phosgene. We have developed safer route for the synthesis of aromatic carbamates using dimethyl carbonate (DMC) as a green reagent.

Background

Present estimated world capacity is ~10 million TPA. Because of highly toxic nature of phosgene, there is a need to develop safer route for these products. Methoxycarbonylation using DMC as green reagent has emerged as popular route in recent time. However, challenge is in developing stable and recyclable catalyst for the reaction..

Process description

The methoxycarbonylation of aniline was carried out in Parr autoclave at high temperature. Methoxycarbonylation of toluenediamine (TDA) and methylene diphenylamine (MDA) will be investigated using same process. Schematic of the reactions is presented below:

Scheme 2: Methyl N phenyl carbamate synthesis from aniline and DMC

Scheme 3: Toluene diurethane synthesis from toluene diamine and DMC

Scheme 4: synthesis of methyl-4,4'-di(phenyl)carbamate from MDA and DMC

The reaction is carried out in a 50 ml Parr reactor at high temperature.

Developed heterogeneous catalyst for the reaction.

Molar ratio of aniline:DMC is important parameter in achieving high conversion of aniline.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process is atom efficient without generation of any salt. Zn-proline was found to be active and selective catalyst and settled at the bottom of the reactor. Catalyst was recycled giving comparable activity.

Technology status:

Work on the development of heterogeneous catalyst has been carried out and zinc-proline complex was found to be active and selective catalyst for the reaction. Catalyst was recycled once without drop in activity and selectivity to MPC. Work carried out so far has led to 99% conversion of aniline with 97% selectivity to MPC. Further work on improving life of the catalyst and expanding the scope of work to TDA and MDA methoxycarbonylation is in progress.

Patents: Patent disclosure submitted to NCP Patent Office.

Publications: Publication will be communicated after filing Indian Patent Application.

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CSIR – National Chemical Laboratory

Synthesis of styrene oxide from styrene

Executive Summary

A bi phasic styrene oxide process is productively taken up to the pilot level synthesis (1 Kg scale reaction plant) by using organic promoter, inorganic base, transition metal catalyst and hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant with 98 % selectivity and >99 % conversion.

Highly efficient method is developed for epoxidation of styrene in aqueous medium that gave excellent yield as well as selectivity of styrene oxide.

Water layer obtained from the previously established epoxidation process containing soluble organic promoter (urea), NaHCO_3 , manganese is successfully reused in next several batches by simple water evaporation in direct sunlight, showing very good recyclability. The aqueous layer can also be absorbed in the fullers' earth powder to use it as efficient urea and manganese based fertiliser.

Background

- Styrene oxide is used in the synthesis of phenyl ethyl alcohol, a key component in fragrance industry.
- Styrene oxide is widely used in food, fragrance and pharmaceuticals industry. There are several products obtained from ring opening of styrene oxide which are of relevant from industrial point of view.
- Since styrene oxide has a chiral center at the benzylic carbon atom, there are (R)-styrene oxide and (S)-styrene oxide. In addition, nucleophiles always attacks the secondary carbon of the oxirane ring because of stability of the intermediate and steric hindrance. If optically pure reagent is used, only one optically pure compound will be obtained.

Process description

This process for the synthesis of styrene oxide developed requires urea, NaHCO_3 , and manganese sulphate.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Excellent conversion and good selectivity
- Easier separation after the completion of reaction
- Does not require any organic solvent

Technology status: The process is licensed to M/s Asian Azoles, Vapi in 2015.

Publications: Patent Filed.

A process for ring-opened glyceryl ricinoleates, epoxy alkyl ricinoleates, and alkyl ricinoleates from castor oil

Executive Summary

Functionalized castor oil derivatives namely ring-opened glyceryl ricinoleates, epoxy alkyl ricinoleates and ring-opened alkyl ricinoleates were successfully prepared with tunable physical properties from epoxidized castor oil (ECO). Two-pot reactions were demonstrated for the preparation of ring-opened alkyl ricinoleates using Amberlyst 15 and LDH derived oxides as efficient heterogeneous acid and base catalysts, respectively. Both catalysts were successfully recycled.

Background

Castor oil is one of promising non-edible oils which is effectively used in many industrial processes for making various chemicals. The oil can be easily oxidized and the epoxides of the oil are valuable intermediates for the production of several chemicals that have many industrial applications. The products derived from fatty epoxides are useful in bioplasticizers, surfactants and coatings, polymers, lubricant additives, hydraulic & dielectric fluids, as antifriction/antioxidant and anti-wear in automotives, polyurethanes and as lubricants.

Process description

The developed process have many advantages in terms of conversion, energy saving (lesser time).

The key process results are:

- Ring opening of ECO with methanol resulted methoxylated castor polyol (MCP with maximum conversion of 82% using Amberlyst 15 (10 wt.% w.r.t. ECO) catalyst at 105 °C. Reaction of ECO with other nucleophiles gave 24-70% conversion of ECO.
- Tranesterification of ECO with methanol gave 91% yield of epoxy methyl ricinoleate (EMR) using LDH derived oxide as catalyst. EMR was further tranesterified with different alcohols that resulted 23-49% yield of epoxy alkyl ricinoleates.
- Two-pot reactions with methanol resulted 78±3% conversion of ECO and 87±4 % yield of tranesterified product– methoxylated methyl ricinoleate (MMR) under the optimized individual reaction conditions.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Simple process for the preparation of castor derivatives, Low cost, highly active, heterogeneous and recyclable catalysts, Simple separation processes
- Maximum conversion of ECO with methanol (82%- 105 °C in 4 h)
- Maximum yield of tranesterified product (EMR-91%)
- Tunable physical properties

Technology status:

Successfully scaled-up at 500 g for MCP and MMR. Samples were sent to M/s Jayant Agro for application potential evaluation. Based on the properties tested for a specified application, MMR showed suitability in terms of viscosity, acid value and application potential. Cost calculations for manufacturing were worked out and shared to decide the applicability of the product in the market.

Patents: IPO Application Number - 2225DEL2014 and PCT/IN2015/050084 dated 6th August 2015

Publications: RSC Advances, 5 (2015) 50289

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CSIR – Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute

Process for the synthesis of 3-methyl-5-phenylpentanol (Mefrosol)

Executive Summary

An efficient process has been developed for the preparation of perfume based compound Mefrosol. This process describes the preparation of arylpentanol derived from the easily available starting materials. This method contains two-step synthetic methodologies for the preparation of Mefrosol. First step involves the treatment of aldehyde with the isoprenol in presence of heterogeneous acidic resin based catalyst and toluene as a solvent. The optimized resin based acid catalysts was found to be effective to catalyse the condensation reaction followed by cyclization step and results in the formation of dihydropyran type compound, Rosyrane with good yield and selectivity. The obtained crude product Rosyrane was used as such without any further purification for the next step with simple Pd/C catalyst in presence of isopropanol as a solvent.

Background

Rosyrane is an industrially fragrance compound. Rosyrane is contain dihydropyran in its structure, which is synthetically useful and an important synthon as it is presence in various natural products such as Lailimalide and (-)-Dactylolide.. Moreover, the synthesis of dihydropyrans are comparatively more attractive since the olefin function can be further functionalized to obtain polysubstitutedpyrans. Rosyrane is intense, diffusive rose character is difficult to separate in the pure form so the process should be highly selective. Moreover, this catalytic process is so sensitive for the reaction parameters like temperature and amount of solvent.

Process description

An efficient catalytic process has been developed for the synthesis of industrially important perfume compound Rosyrane (4-methyl-2-phenyl-3,6-dihydro-2H-pyran). In this context, initially we tried with a silica supported heterogeneous acid catalyst, though it is efficient and resulted in excellent conversion and high selectivity, but the catalyst is not bench stable, this makes the catalytic process tedious for scale up studies. Now we are develop this process by using industrially available resin based acid catalyst for the synthesis of Rosyrane. In this process, various types of acid based catalyst was screened for this reaction. Further optimization studies using the resin based catalyst resulted in excellent conversion (>99%) with selectivity (90%). The advantage of the catalyst is it is bench stable and regioselective. The second step involves the one pot reaction of hydrogenation and hydrogenolysis of dihydropyran compound in presence of Pd/C catalyst to give the perfume based compound 3-methyl-5-phenylpentanol. In this one pot reaction various parameters like catalyst loading, temperature, pressure, solvent and amount of solvent plays a crucial factor to achieve good conversion and selectivity. Conversion(>99%) and selectivity (90%).

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Low catalyst loading
- Excellent conversion and good selectivity
- Easier separation after the completion of reaction
- Best results in synthesis of Rosyrane and Mefrosol without using any external acid additives and any bimetallic systems

Technology status: Laboratory scale processon 250 g for first step and 10 g for second step is developed. Sample is sent to M/s Aquila Organics, Mumbai (after the first step) for separation issues followed by hydrogenation at their end (Pure isolated Mefrosol is also sent).

Publications: Patent Filed (CSIR NF Number: 235NF2015)

Process for γ -valerolactone by hydrogenation of levulinic acid

Executive Summary

An improved process for the preparation of γ -valerolactone (Gvl) by catalytic hydrogenation of biomass-derived levulinic acid (LA) is developed. This process renders excellent yield (100%) under mild reaction conditions in short reaction time in aqueous medium using recyclable Ru-based heterogeneous catalysts. In comparison with prior art including those reported using Ru-based catalysts, the disclosed catalysts here have improved activity and reusability for several cycles, less energy demanding, conserving optimal utility of raw materials and need shorter time.

Background

Levulinic acid (LA), one of the identified 12 building block molecules from biomass by U.S. One of the value-chain compounds of LA is γ -valerolactone (Gvl) which finds extensive application as eco-friendly solvent, fuel precursor and additives, in polymers and as intermediate for diverse chemicals. Gvl can be prepared via catalytic hydrogenation of LA. This conversion is important for a sustainable bio-refinery. Despite significant work worldwide, till date no catalytic process has been reported to be effective near ambient conditions in shorter time with high yields.

Process description

The process for preparation of Gvl involves catalytic hydrogenation of levulinic acid using molecular hydrogen using 'in situ' generated ruthenium catalyst either in its neat or supported forms. These catalysts were active under near ambient conditions and renders stoichiometric yields of Gvl. Some of the representative conditions highlighting the process are given below:

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Reactions under mild conditions (50-100 oC and 5 - 15 atm. pressure of H₂)
- Nearly 100% conversion of LA, Excellent selectivity for Gvl (100%)
- Lesser reaction time (2-30 min)
- Using lesser weight % of precious metal, here Ru, content
- Reactions using heterogeneous catalysts
- No necessity of prior reduction of the active catalyst and is in situ generated
- Active catalyst is recyclable
- Reactions in aqueous medium
- Requirement of nearly stoichiometric quantity of hydrogen thereby avoiding recycle operations
- The active catalyst can be supported on inexpensive supports such as zeolites and LDHs for efficient recovery and reuse

Technology status:

Successfully scaled-up to 20 g, and planning to scale-up 2 kg batch. Discussed with M/s Praj Industries, Pune and other industries. Awaiting for publishing of patent application to take further.

Patents: IPO Application Number - 2866DEL2014; PCT/IN2015/050130 (October 2015).

Publications: Manuscript under communication (Part of the work is presented at 3rd International Symposium on Green Chemistry, La Rochelle, France (May 2015) & SusChemE (October 2015))

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Chemo- and regioselective synthesis of arylated γ -valerolactones

Executive Summary

Novel arylated γ -valerolactones (Agvl) were synthesized from biomass derived levulinic acid (LA) using H- β zeolite as recyclable catalyst. The reaction is highly chemo- and regioselective rendering selectively (80-90%) the para-substituted lactone. The reaction was demonstrated on 10 g scale and after 24 h, the yield of para isomer of γ -lactone reached up to 62%.

Background

Levulinic acid (LA), one of the biomass derived keto carboxylic acid, plays an important role in the synthesis of valuable chemicals and fuels via diverse catalytic organic transformation. LA is readily obtained from most abundant cellulosic biomass via sugar-based carbohydrates (C6/C5) such as sawdust, paper mill sludge, tobacco chops, sugarcane bagasse and wheat by the acid-catalyzed depolymerization and dehydration reactions followed by hydration using various homogeneous/heterogeneous catalysts. In the present process, a synthetic protocol was developed for the preparation of various arylated γ -lactones using modified β -zeolite as recyclable heterogeneous catalyst under milder reaction condition without using any solvent.

Process description

Screening of catalysts and optimization of reaction parameters were carried out. Key results are:

- When the aromatics used are thiophene, alkoxy aryl ethers and thio ethers, the reaction selectively proceeded over H- β to yield agvls by nucleophilic addition followed by cyclisation
- The reaction is highly chemo- and regioselective
- The reaction did not proceed for para-substituted alkoxybenzenes such as 1-ethoxy-4-methoxybenzene ascertains para selectivity
- The synthesized new value chain γ -lactones are highly stable in open atmosphere

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Reactions under milder conditions (80-150 °C)
- Reactions under open atmosphere
- Good conversion and yields
- Use of recyclable heterogeneous catalysts
- Use of excess aromatic in the reaction medium that acts as solvent and enhance the kinetics of the reaction with excellent selectivity that could be recycled
- Good chemo- and regio- selectivity for the preparation of agvls.
- The prepared products of LA have structural accessibility to develop applications in the field of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals and fuel industry.
- Some of the synthesized compounds are novel in nature (we believe they are synthesized for the first time in the world)

Technology status:

Successfully scaled-up 10 g (LA with anisole). Further scale-up studies and identification of application prospects/industry are underway.

Patents: Indian Patent Office Application Number - 170NF2015 (August 2015).

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Oxidation of n-octanol to octyloctanoate

Executive Summary

- Oxidation of *n*-Octanol to Octyl octanoate using bromide and bromate mixture under aqueous conditions has been achieved at room temperature.
- Separation is easy through phase separation of aqueous and organic after completion of the reaction.
- The aqueous effluent contains HBr which could be recovered as a value added product.

Background

The carboxylic acid ester is an important organic compounds, not only used as an organic synthesis as raw materials but also an important fine chemical product widely used in perfumes, foods, and other industrial applications. Traditional synthetic methods carboxylic acid ester is the corresponding carboxylic acid and alcohol as raw materials, catalysts are poly brominated salts and use of organic solvents are corrosive, and also externally adding the bases to the reaction mixtures and high temperature, oxidants are also used for their individual process. In the present process bromide-bromate couple in aqueous acidic medium is used to generate BrOH species as the oxidant, for the oxidation. This process not only can reduce the synthetic steps but also avoids organic solvents.

Process description

The selective conversion of octanol to its corresponding ester using different bromide sources with catalytic amount of mineral acid at room temperature has been developed. Among bromide sources studied, 2:1 bromide/bromate with sulfuric acid was found to be the best combination for the present transformation. After completion of the reaction, the product could be easily purified by extraction of DCE and removal of solvent. The method yield quantitatively the desired product. This method is also applicable to obtain the other aliphatic esters (C6-C10 studied).

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Reaction carried out at room temperature
- Easy to handle
- Product could be purified by simple extraction
- Quantitative yields

Technology status:

Laboratory scale (50 g) process has been developed.

Patents: Patent filed in January 2016 – CSIR NF Number - 23NF2016

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CSIR – Central Salt & Marine Chemicals Research Institute

Synthesis of α -hexyl cinnamaldehyde (hexyl cinnamal) from *n*-octanal and benzaldehyde by using heterogeneous catalyst

Executive Summary

The cross aldol condensation synthesis of hexyl cinnamaldehyde from *n*-octanal and benzaldehyde was successfully investigated up to 100 g with respect to *n*-octanal. Hexyl Cinnamaldehyde was productively synthesized by taking 1:3-mole ratio of *n*-octanal and benzaldehyde respectively by using heterogeneous catalyst under nitrogen atmosphere at 100-200°C temperature in 5-10 h.

Background

α -Hexylcinnamaldehyde is found naturally in the essential oil of chamomile. It is an aroma substance and a common additive in perfume and cosmetic industry. Existing processes for the synthesis of hexyl cinnamaldehyde requires higher benzaldehyde:*n*-octanal mole ratio to avoid self-condensation of *n*-octanal. Further, it requires a strong base as a catalyst which suffers from the separation and environment problems.

Process description

Synthesis of α -Hexyl cinnamaldehyde from *n*-octanal and benzaldehyde by taking 10 weight % catalyst has been successfully developed at 100-200 °C with dropwise addition of *n*-octanal to benzaldehyde in duration of 5-10 h under nitrogen atmosphere.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Requires very less catalyst amount
- Catalyst can be recovered by simple filtration after the completion of reaction
- Does not require any organic solvent (for the reaction)

Technology status: Further optimization and scale-up is being done. Industry is identified for licensing this process and discussions are underway.

Publications: Patent filing is under progress.

A process for 2,3-dihydrofuran from cis-1,4-but-2-enediol

Executive Summary

2,3-dihydrofuran (2,3-DHF) is an important compound used as an intermediate in the preparation of anticancer drugs and biologically important molecules. The preparation of 2,3-DHF involves two reaction steps namely, dehydration of cis-1,4-but-2-enediol (BDO) to 2,5-DHF followed by isomerization of 2,5-DHF to 2,3-DHF using different sets of catalysts. Amberlyst-15 showed good selectivity (68%) of 2,5-DHF from BDO in γ -valerolactone (GVL) as solvent medium. The crushed 0.5% Pd/Al₂O₃ isomerization catalyst showed a maximum conversion of 2,5-DHF with good selectivity (90%) of 2,3-DHF under milder conditions. Selectivity for the desired 2,5-DHF and 2,3-DHF was improved further by optimizing reaction conditions such as time and particle size of catalyst. An approach is also attempted to distil out the volatile DHF (and water) from reaction mixture by applying vacuum to shift the reaction which is otherwise equilibrium limited/controlled.

Background

In literature, 2,3-DHF, is reported to be prepared by using cobalt-based supported catalysts sometimes promoted with noble metals such as gold or palladium. The main disadvantage of using the above catalysts is the necessity of high reaction temperature (>250 °C) given the fact that the boiling points of these cyclic furans are very low. Although one pot synthesis of 2,3-DHF from butanediol or cis-1,4-but-2-enediol (commercially both sources are sold at nearly similar price), the reaction is challenging considering low stability of 2,3-DHF in the reaction mixture, and the negative influence of the by-product water on the catalyst performance.

Process description

The process being developed involves carrying out the reaction in two steps (delinking one from the other thereby avoiding the detrimental influence of water) namely dehydration of cis-1,4-but-2-enediol to 2,5-DHF and isomerizing thus obtained 2,5-DHF to 2,3-DHF.

The key process results are:

- Amberlyst-15 gave good yields of 2,5-DHF (~76%) in GVL solvent at 80°C
- 0.5% Pd on alumina showed a maximum yield of 2,3-DHF (75%) with good selectivity (90%) from 2,5-DHF; Low loading of catalyst, less expensive among many Pd based catalysts, and easy to separate
- Continuous removal of 2,5-DHF and water from the reaction mixture was possible with ~80% recovery by applying vacuum in controlled manner
- Simple, innovative and energy efficient process for the preparation of 2,5-DHF and 2,3-DHF

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Use of biomass-derived GVL as reaction medium (green process)
- Use of low cost, highly active, recyclable, commercially available heterogeneous catalysts
- Adopting continuous process with simple separation via distillation for improved efficiency

Technology status:

Scaling up, improving recovery via reactive separation and use of combined catalysts are in progress. M/s Aether Industries has shown interest on this project and would be taken further on having promising results.

Patents: Filing will be done after successful scale-up and integration studies

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CSIR – Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute

Synthesis of Jasminaldehyde from n-heptanal and benzaldehyde

Executive Summary

The cross aldol condensation synthesis of jasminaldehyde from n-heptanal and benzaldehyde was successfully investigated up to 50 g scale with respect to n-heptanal. Jasminaldehyde was synthesized by taking 1:5 mole ratio of n-heptanal and benzaldehyde respectively by using heterogeneous catalyst under nitrogen atmosphere at 100-150 °C in 10-24 h.

Background

α -Pentylcinnamaldehyde (commonly called jasminaldehyde) is found naturally in the essential oil of jasmine. It is an aroma substance and a common additive in perfumes and cosmetic industry. Existing processes for the synthesis of α -pentylcinnamaldehyde requires more benzaldehyde:n-heptanal ratio to avoid self-condensation of n-heptanal and also require a strong base as a catalyst which suffers with the separation and environment problems.

Process description

Synthesis of α -Pentyl cinnamaldehyde from n-heptanal and benzaldehyde by taking required amount of heterogeneous basic catalyst has been successfully developed at 100-150 °C with dropwise addition of n-heptanal to benzaldehyde in duration of 10-24 h under nitrogen atmosphere.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Requires lesser amount of catalyst
- Ease of separation of catalyst after completing of reaction
- Solvent free system

Technology status: Further optimization and scale-up is being done.

Publications: Patent filing is under progress.

Synthesis of β -bromostyrene from styrene bromohydrin

Executive Summary

- Synthesis of β -bromostyrene from styrene bromohydrin using H- β -zeolite as a heterogeneous catalyst under moderate conditions has been developed.
- The method offers the selective intramolecular dehydration to lead the product without waste generation.
- The catalyst could be regenerated and reused up to three consecutive cycles without appreciable loss of catalytic activity.
- The conventional process involve through decarboxylative bromination of cinnamic acid using NBS as brominating agent, which generates succinimide as organic by-product.
- The present process generates only water as by-product.

Background

The traditional methods for the synthesis of β -bromostyrene are through the classical Hunsdiecker reaction involving the halo decarboxylation of cinnamic acid derivatives, olefination of aromatic aldehydes, homologation of benzyl bromides with dihalomethanes, and reduction of 1,1-dihaloalkenes, and metal complexes of styrenes with halogen analogues. However, these methods are cumbersome and uneconomical.

Process description

The present process offers selective dehydration of styrene bromohydrin to β -bromostyrene using catalytic amount of commercially available H- β -zeolite as heterogeneous and reusable catalyst under mild reaction conditions. The present approach highlights a useful alternative to the traditional Hunsdiecker reaction involving the halo decarboxylation of cinnamic acid derivatives. Notably, water is the only by-product generated make this transformation more atom-economical and greener, than the traditional methods.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Atom efficiency and no by-product formation [only water is eliminated in the process]
- H- β -zeolite catalyst is inexpensive and commercially available
- Easy separation of the catalyst and it can be reused up to three consecutive cycles without appreciable loss of catalytic activity

Technology status: Laboratory scale (5.0 g) process has been developed.

Publications: P. Venkatanarayana, D. Ramachandra Reddy, D. Chandra Mohan and S. Adimurthy*
Tetrahedron Lett. **2014**, *55*, 1793-1795.

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CSIR – Central Salt & Marine Chemicals Research Institute

Resolution of metallohelicates

Executive Summary

- The method for resolution of enantiomers in metallohelicates was developed.
- A series of Co(II) and Ni(II) binuclear double stranded helicates are synthesized and resolved into $\Delta\Delta$ and $\Lambda\Lambda$ enantiomers.
- The enantiomers are applied as stereoselective catalyst for asymmetric organic transformations.

Background

Resolving metallohelicates into $\Delta\Delta$ and $\Lambda\Lambda$ enantiomers provides opportunity to be employed them as stereoselective (or chiral) catalyst for asymmetric organic transformation, however, is challenging.

Process description

The binuclear double stranded metallohelicates were synthesized and are resolved into $\Delta\Delta$ and $\Lambda\Lambda$ enantiomers. This can be achieved by chiral stationary and mobile phase. Initially column chromatography was adopted for the separation process. The main drawback is time consuming process and ended up with one enantiomer. This was overcome by dialysis techniques, which reduces the time significantly from 25 days to 10 hours. The compounds were made slurry using cellulose and loaded into cellulose membrane and allowed to stir in an aqueous solution containing 20% potassium tartrate (0.02 M) with acetonitrile. The solution is evaporated; the excess tartrate is removed by methanol wash. The tartrate is replaced by metathesis using ammonium hexafluorophosphate and found the chirality is retained. All the complexes were crystallographically established for their structure and the chiral property was confirmed by CD spectroscopy.

The key process steps are:

- The simple and efficient methods are adopted for synthesis of metallohelicates
- The metallohelicates are resolved into $\Delta\Delta$ and $\Lambda\Lambda$ enantiomers by dialysis techniques
- The dialysis technique appears to be superior and efficient than column chromatography

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The asymmetric carbon-free chiral catalysts were developed. The significance of the materials will depend upon the applications in asymmetric catalysis. The catalytic activities of the resolved metallohelicates are proven by their enantioselective catalysis following nitroaldol reaction and 54% ee was achieved at -50°C in methanol-THF system.

Technology status:

The process of resolution of enantiomers in laboratory scale is developed. The scale-up batches and catalytic applications of these resolved metallohelicates are in progress.

Publications:

R.Arunachalam, C.S. Aswathi, Anjan Das, R.I. Kureshy and P.S. Subramanian,* Diastereoselective nitroaldol reaction catalyzed by binuclear Cu(II) complexes in aqueous medium, *ChemPlusChem*, 2015, 80, 209-216.

E.Chinnaraja, R.Arunachalam, M.K. Chaudhri, R.I. Kureshy and P.S. Subramanian*, Binuclear Cu(II) chiral complexes: Synthesis, characterization and its application in enantioselective nitroaldol (Henry) reaction, *Appl. Organometal Chem.* 2015.

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Synthesis of Di-octyl phthalate by heterogeneous acid catalysis

Executive Summary

- Synthesis of dioctyl phthalate (DOP) via esterification of phthalic acid/anhydride and 1-/2-octanol has been done by heterogeneous acid catalysis to replace conventional acids.
- The conventional process using concentrated H₂SO₄ or *p*-TSA generates acidic waste and needs extra post-treatment step.
- DOP is one of the industrially important phthalateplasticizer, extensively used in the manufacture of PVC and ethyl cellulose resin based materials such as plastic films, electric wires, imitation leather, blood bags, dialysis equipment and also in paints.

Background

DOP is the most common low-phthalate plasticizer used worldwide. It is most widely used in Asia and Latin America. The heterogeneous synthesis provides key advantages over conventional homogeneous process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The heterogeneous catalysis is based on sulfated zirconia (SZr) as solid acid catalyst, which exhibited higher activity for esterification of phthalic acid and *n*-octanol among zeolite, clay, resin based acid catalysts (shown in the Table).

The key process steps are:

- Optimal synthetic parameters for enhancing selectivity towards DOP have been established.
- Water formed during the reaction was removed to carry the reaction in forward direction.
- After reaction, catalyst was removed by simple filtration or centrifugation.
- Pure DOP (yellowish liquid) was obtained after removing unreacted substrates, i.e., phthalic acid and alcohol by neutralization and distillation steps, respectively.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process achieves 88% conversion of *n*-octanol with 93% selectivity of DOP, which is comparable/ similar to conventional homogeneous process using *p*-TSA and H₂SO₄ with the advantage of environmental footprint (no sulfuric acid, no solvent) and easily separable, re-usable, eco-friendly heterogeneous acid catalyst.

Technology status: Laboratory scale-up studies for 100 g DOP were done.

Publications: Under communication

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CSIR – CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, Gujarat

Synthesis of α -pinene oxide from α -pinene in aqueous phase

Executive Summary

A bi-phasic epoxidation process for the synthesis of α -pinene oxide from α -pinene by using organic catalyst, inorganic base, transition metal catalyst, tert-butanol as phase transfer agent and hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant with more than 99% conversion and upto 70% selectivity is developed.

Background

Pinene oxide is a fragrance compound found in plants and essential oils. It is very important in pharmaceutical and flavoring materials, used in tooth paste, detergent, and shampoos. There are several products obtained from ring opening of pinene oxide which are of relevance from industrial point of view.

Process description

This process for the synthesis of pinene oxide developed requires organic catalyst, NaHCO_3 , and manganese sulphate.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Excellent conversion
- Require lesser time

Technology status: Further optimization and scale-up studies are in progress.

A process for the preparation of cyclamenaldehyde

Executive Summary

A reaction methodology has been developed for the preparation of cyclamenaldehyde through condensation followed by hydrogenation. Among the catalysts studied for the condensation reaction between isopropylbenzaldehyde (IPB) and propanal (PA), K_2CO_3 showed the best catalytic activity with 80% of intermediate product under milder reaction conditions. The selectivity was further improved by optimizing the reactor and conditions to 95%. Furthermore, hydrogenation of the intermediate was successfully demonstrated to cyclamenaldehyde with a maximum conversion and selectivity using commercially available 5% Pd/C under mild reaction conditions.

Background

Cyclamenaldehyde is a fragrance molecule, not naturally found, (Floral, green, powerful - used in floral, green, fresh and marine accords) used in products like soaps, detergents, and house hold products. It is also used in functional perfumery and masking agents in cosmetics due its stability and substantivity. It is prepared by the cross aldol condensation of IPB and PA followed by hydrogenation in the presence of catalysts. Commercially, it is produced in a conventional batch process using alkali in the first step of condensation and Pd/charcoal or Raney nickel for the hydrogenation step. A US Patent assigned to Soda Koryo Kabushiki Kaisha, Japan however claims to synthesize cyclamenaldehyde through vapour phase hydrogenation of *p*-isopropyl-methyl cinnamic aldehyde in the temperature range 150-500 °C under reduced pressure to effect selective hydrogenation of double bond to *p*-isopropyl-methyl hydrocinnamic aldehyde (cyclamenaldehyde).

Process description

Synthesis of cyclamenaldehyde was achieved through a two-step reaction protocol. In first step, condensation reaction between isopropyl benzaldehyde and propanal was carried out at 27 °C using methanol as solvent and K_2CO_3 as catalyst that gave 86% conversion and 80% selectivity for condensed intermediate. The selectivity was further improved to 95% while carrying out the reaction in EasyMax Reaction System. The second step involving hydrogenation has been carried out successfully and is being validated on relatively larger scale.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Both steps use heterogeneous catalysts (avoiding conventional homogeneous corrosive catalysts for the condensation step) and in particular, the second step uses a commercial catalyst and thus sourcing can be easier.
- Excellent selectivity for the hydrogenation step suggests the reaction is chemoselective.
- Reasonably high yield of cyclamenaldehyde is achieved.

Technology status: Scale-up studies for both steps are in progress.

Patents: Will be filed if scale-up results are promising.

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CSIR – Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute

A process for cuminaldehyde using tert-butyl hydroperoxide as oxidant

Executive Summary

Liquid phase oxidation of *p*-cymene using *t*-butyl hydroperoxide (TBHP) as oxidant to selectively synthesize *p*-isopropyl benzaldehyde (PIPB) over CoAl-based layered double hydroxides and CuCr oxides were carried out. The catalyst with Co/Al atomic ratio 3.0 gave a maximum conversion of 43% with 38% selectivity of *p*-isopropyl benzyl alcohol (PIBOH) and 6% selectivity of PIPB and trace amount of *p*-methylacetophenone at 140 °C in 5 h using 1:2.7 mole ratio of *p*-cymene:TBHP. Among oxide catalysts, CuCr₂O₄ gave a maximum conversion of 22% with 40% selectivity of *p*-methylacetophenone (PMAP) and 15% selectivity of PIPB and trace amount of PIBOH at 100 °C in 24 h using 3:6.83 mole ratio of *p*-cymene:TBHP.

Background

Oxidation reactions play main role in chemical industries as more than 60% of products are obtained through this reaction. Liquid phase oxidations of alkyl aromatic hydrocarbons are important reactions for the synthesis of highly valuable intermediates in the specialty chemical industry. Liquid phase oxidation of *p*-cymene (4-isopropyltoluene) results two predominant intermediates namely tertiary cymene hydroperoxide (TCHP) & primary cymene hydroperoxide (PCHP) which subsequently converts into oxidation products such as PMAP, PIBOH, PIPB and 4-isopropyl benzoic acid, that serve as important building block for other value added products. PMAP is a valuable chemical in the perfume industry, whereas PIPB is mainly used as a flavouring agent in the food industry. Selective oxidation to the desired product, PIPB, a starting material for cyclamenaldehyde, a well-known perfumery chemical is a challenge. The most reported route for the preparation of PIPB is the oxidation of PIBOH.

Process description

The key process results for the preparation of PIPB from *p*-cymene by catalytic oxidation are given below:

- Among the CoAl-LDHs studied with varying Co/Al atomic ratios, the catalyst with Co/Al atomic ratio 3.0 gave a maximum conversion of 43% with 38% selectivity of *p*-isopropyl benzyl alcohol (PIBOH) and 6% selectivity of PIPB and trace amount of *p*-methylacetophenone at 140 °C in 5 h using 1:2.7 mole ratio of *p*-cymene:TBHP.
- Among the oxide catalysts, CuCr₂O₄ gave moderate conversion (66%) with low selectivity of *p*-isopropyl benzaldehyde (8%) and good selectivity of *p*-methyl acetophenone (59%).
- Solvent variation studies indicated a maximum selectivity of PIPB (15%) in DMF while maximum conversion (81%) in chlorobenzene.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Low cost heterogamous catalyst
- Easy separation of the catalysts
- Liquid-phase reaction

Technology status: Further improvement in the selectivity is necessary.

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CSIR – Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute

A process for ricinoleyl alcohol

Executive Summary

Selective hydrogenation of methyl ricinoleate (MR) to ricinoleyl alcohol is an interesting and important reaction as the starting material can be sourced from castor oil. However, it is challenging to hydrogenate ester group of methyl ricinoleate to ricinoleyl alcohol without affecting double bond of MR; the reaction product ricinoleyl alcohol has many utility in industry and hence design of heterogeneous catalysts for the conversion will have significant impact in bio-based oil industries, in particular castor industry. In the process being developed, low cost heterogeneous catalysts are used as catalysts for the preparation of ricinoleyl alcohol using molecular hydrogen. Preliminary experiments rendered double bond hydrogenated product (12-hydroxy methyl stearate) in 100% yield using Ru/ H₃PW₁₂O₄₀/SBA-15.

Background

Castor oil is one of the promising non-edible oils which is effectively used in many industrial processes for making various chemicals. In world, ~60,000 tonnes of castor oil are produced every year (as of 2012) and India occupies the top place for castor production with nearly ~60%. Presence of >85% of ricinoleic acid (a functionalized fatty derivative which has ester linkage, hydroxyl group and unsaturated centre) makes castor oil an important raw material for various commercial applications. Ricinoleyl alcohol is mainly used in the production of surfactants, cosmetics, co-emulsifiers, emollients, detergents, and in food industry. Due to amphipathic nature, ricinoleyl alcohols behave as nonionic surfactants. Methyl ricinoleate can be one of the promising raw materials for the production of ricinoleyl alcohol that can be obtained via hydrogenation in presence of heterogeneous catalysts.

Process description

Selective hydrogenation of methyl ricinoleate to ricinoleyl alcohol

The key process results are:

In presence of isopropyl alcohol as solvent, hydrogenation of methyl ricinoleate rendered selective formation of 12-hydroxy methyl stearate as product with 100% selectivity and 100% conversion using Ru/H₃PW₁₂O₄₀/SBA-15. Efforts are underway to control the hydrogenation without affecting the other functional groups.

Salient features/ Advantages aimed over existing processes

- Low cost, highly active, selective heterogeneous and recyclable catalysts
- Simple separation processes
- Moderate reaction conditions
- Support active catalyst over zeolites or LDHs for efficient recovery and reuse

Technology status: Design and deployment of catalysts for selective hydrogenation is critical

Development of low cost and effective heterogeneous catalytic process for the preparation of vanillin from isoeugenol

Executive Summary

Vanillin is an important aroma chemical finds industrial applications. Preparation of vanillin from isoeugenol by oxidative cleavage is an interesting reaction because the starting material can also be obtained from lignin source. In the developed process, low cost hydrotalcite-like material was used as effective catalyst for the preparation of vanillin using H_2O_2 as oxidant source. At 90 °C and within 5 h 30% of vanillin was selectively obtained from isoeugenol using CuFe-HT as catalyst.

Background

Vanillin is an important aroma compound (produced in the earlier years through extraction from vanilla plant; although now produced through petrochemical route) and their market value is continuously increasing due to their increasing industrial importance. Isoeugenol can be one of the promising raw material for the production of vanillin, wherein the latter can be achieved by simple oxidative cleavage in presence of heterogeneous catalysts. In literature largely either homogeneous catalysis or enzymatic catalysis is employed for the oxidative cleavage. For example, $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NVO}_3$ /pyrazine-2-carboxylic acid catalytic combination gave 50% yield of vanillin in 2 h at 80 °C, with a turnover number around 1200. Cobalt porphyrin complexes have also been employed using oxygen as oxidant with low conversion and moderate selectivity (~72%).

Process description

The key process results are:

- The developed process/approach uses low cost hydrotalcite-like materials as heterogeneous catalyst for the preparation of vanillin from isoeugenol
- In presence of CuFe-HT and with multiple addition of H_2O_2 , isoeugenol was selectively converted to vanillin in moderate yields at 90 °C in 5 h

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Low cost catalyst
- H_2O_2 as benign oxidant (as the product is water)
- Selective product formation

Technology status: Viable if isoeugenol is sourced from lignin via oxidative cleavage.

A continuous process for the preparation of 1-octene from castor oil derived 2-octanol over heterogeneous acid catalysts

Executive Summary

1-octene is an important co-monomer used in the preparation of linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE) polymer. Dehydration of castor oil derived 2-octanol leads to the formation of 1-octene in presence of acidic catalysts. Various acidic catalysts (commercial as well as synthesized) were used for this dehydration reaction in a continuous (BTRS reactor) system. At a 2-octanol flow rate of 0.1 ml/min, acidic alumina gave >90% conversion with 23% yield of 1-octene at 275 °C in presence of N₂ as carrier gas. Other catalysts such as zirconia, zeolite, montmorillonite, resin catalysts, activated carbon showed lesser conversion than acidic alumina.

Background

Linear alpha olefins are important building block chemical for many industrial processes. All the linear olefins are currently produced from petroderived route only. Developing a process for linear olefins from biomass-derived molecules is an interesting area of research besides providing sustainable option. 1-octene is one of the important linear olefins which finds application in linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE) polymer preparation. 2-octanol is an important molecule derived from non-edible castor oil source that can be used for the preparation of 1-octene.

Process description

The key process results are:

- The developed process dealt with the continuous production of 1-octene from castor oil derived 2-octanol using acidic catalysts.
- Acidic alumina gave >90% conversion with 23% yield of 1-octene at 275 °C while using 2-octanol flow rate of 0.1 ml/min.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

- Biomass derived raw material
- Low cost solid acid catalyst
- Continuous process

Technology status: Further experiments have to be done to improve yield of 1-octene.

Catalytic Process for Synthesis of Glycidol from Glycerol

Executive Summary

- A solid base catalyst for the single step synthesis of glycidol from glycerol is developed.
- Glycidol is widely used as a raw material for the preparation of glycidyl ethers, polyglycerols, polyurethanes and pharmaceuticals. It has application in cosmetics, detergents, paints, demulsifiers and dye-leveling agents.
- Glycidol is commercially produced by epichlorohydrin reaction with basic media or epoxidation of allyl alcohol using tungsten based catalyst. Glycidol can also be synthesized from the decarboxylation of glycerol carbonate which can be prepared from glycerol
- The developed process is related to the preparation of glycidol in a single step using heterogeneous catalyst from glycerol instead of two step process involving glycerol to glycerol carbonate and conversion of glycerol carbonate to glycidol.

Background

Utilization of largely available glycerol as a byproduct from biofuel industries is essential. There is a need to develop catalytic process to convert glycerol in to chemicals like glycidol. The catalytic process developed here provides key advantages over conventional process. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process is a single step synthesis of glycidol from glycerol using simple supported solid base catalysts as shown below.

The key process steps are:

- Preparation of the catalyst is simple with easily available raw materials.
- Single step synthesis directly from glycerol under mild reaction condition with in short reaction time.
- Optimum reaction conditions and catalyst amount were established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

In this process the yield of glycidol was about 87% with complete conversion of glycerol at 90 °C within 90 min of reaction time. The other product is glycerol carbonate only. Besides these, the developed process offers several advantages such as easy separation of catalysts and its reusability. Compared to other reported processes where glycidol is prepared from glycerol carbonate. Compared to reported catalysts the present catalysts gave higher activity for the preparation of glycidol from glycerol.

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. The catalyst preparation was optimized at 20 g scale. Scale-up studies are going on.

Patents: Indian Patent filed

Publications: Catalysis Science & Technology, 3 (2013) 3242–3249

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CSIR – Indian Institute of Chemical Technology

Catalytic Process for Glycerol Carbonate from Glycerol and Urea

Executive Summary

- A selective solid catalyst for synthesis of glycerol carbonate from glycerol and urea is developed.
- glycerol carbonate (4-hydroxymethyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-one) is one of the most promising chemical, due to its ideal physico chemical properties such as high stability, low toxicity, good biodegradability, high boiling point and low inflammability. Glycerol carbonate has many applications in the synthesis of polycarbonates, polyurethanes, surfactants, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics.
- Several routes have been reported for the synthesis of glycerol carbonate from glycerol using different carbonyl sources. Glycerol carbonate can be prepared by i) transesterification of glycerol with dialkyl carbonates, ii) reaction of glycerol with carbon monoxide and oxygen, iii) reaction of glycerol with carbon dioxide, iv) from glycerol and phosgene, and v) reaction of glycerol with urea.

Background

Utilization of largely available glycerol as a byproduct from biofuel industries is essential. There is a need to develop catalytic process to convert glycerol in to chemicals like glycerol carbonate. Preparation of glycerol carbonate from glycerol and urea is favourable route in terms of raw materials cost and environmental aspects. The selective catalytic process developed here provides a simple and effective method. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The developed process is a single step synthesis of glycerol carbonate from glycerol and urea using simple metal oxide catalysts as shown below.

The key process steps are:

- Utilization of simple oxides as catalysts and preparation of catalyst is simple and reproducible.
- Selective syntheses of glycerol carbonate from glycerol and urea under mild reaction condition with in short reaction time.
- Optimum reaction conditions were established.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

In this process the yield of glycerol carbonate was about 73% at 140 °C within 4 h of reaction time. In this process we used different simple catalytic systems with varying selectivity and conversion. The developed process offers several advantages such as easy separation of catalysts and its reusability.

Technology status:

Laboratory scale process developed. The catalyst preparation was optimized at 20 g scale. Scale-up studies are going on. Efforts are made to make it as continuous process.

Patents: Under preparation

Publications: Applied Catalysis A: General, 469 (2014) 165-175 ; Catalysis Letters, 145 (2015)1784-1791

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CSIR – Indian Institute of Chemical Technology

Process for *para-tert*-Butyl benzoic acid(PTBBA)

Executive Summary

- *para-tert*-butyl benzoic acid from *para-tert*-butyl toluene is an industrial process based on oxidation catalyzed by cobalt catalyst is developed.
- *para-tert*-butyl benzoic acid is widely used as a catalyst and an additive for cooling lubricant and antioxidant.
- The process developed uses commercial air as oxidant and the catalyst is recycled back after every run along with the mother liquor. The product crystals are washed and dried to obtain the required purity.

Background

The current demand of PTBBA in the Indian market is solely met through imports. At present, PTBBA is not manufactured at large scale by the Indian industry. M/s VOL, Mumbai is producing isobutylene at their manufacturing site and would like to utilize the isobutylene for the production of value added chemicals.

Process description

The reaction is carried out at the desired reaction conditions in an autoclave. Air is continuously fed to the reactor. After the reaction is over, the contents of the reactor are cooled, depressurized, discharged, weighed and collected for further treatment. The downstream processing involves recovery of 4-*tert*-butyl benzoic acid crystals and recycle of mother liquor with catalyst, for the subsequent runs. All the products were identified by GC/MS and analysed by GC on FID detector using ZB-5 column. The conversion achieved was 95%.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process developed uses commercial air as oxidant and the catalyst is recycled back after every run along with the mother liquor. The product crystals are washed and dried to obtain the required purity.

Technology status:

The process developed at CSIR-IICT is by oxidation of *para-tert*-butyl toluene to *para-tert*-butyl benzoic acid. The process was developed at bench scale and demonstrated to M/s VOL, in a batch mode in March 2013. Subsequently, an agreement for scale-up studies and Basic Design Report (BDR) for Commercial Plant of 10 TPD for *para-tert*-butyl benzoic acid was signed. The design for a pilot unit for a 100 kg batch reactor was submitted to the client. Based on the designs the pilot unit was erected at IICT premises. The pilot scale demonstration was completed in February 2014. Data for Basic Design Report for a Commercial Plant of 10 TPD capacity was generated at pilot scale. The Designs for Commercial Plant completed and BDR submitted in June 2014.

Patents: Provisional Patent applied to Indian Patent Office.

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CSIR – Indian Institute of Chemical Technology

Process for *para-tert*-Butyl methyl benzoate(PTBMB)

Executive Summary

- The process for esterification of *para-tert* butyl benzoic acid (PTBBA) to *para-tert* butyl methyl benzoate (PTBMB) using recyclable catalyst is developed
- Methyl benzoate is widely used as UV- absorbent and sunscreen agent and in the preparation of *para-tert*-butyl benzaldehyde (PTBA).
- The process is normally catalyzed by strong minerals or Lewis acids. The existing processes suffer from severe environmental restrictions due to the use of large quantities of strong acids.

Background

At present, PTBMB is not manufactured at large scale by the Indian industry. M/S VOL is interested in producing a value added product (*para-tert*-butyl-methyl benzoate) from *para-tert*-butyl benzoic acid.

Process description

The reaction is carried out at desired reaction conditions in a jacketed stirred vessel equipped with an overhead stirrer and a vent condenser. The reaction progress is followed by analysis of ester formed and un-reacted PTBBA using GC. After completion of reaction the product mixture is cooled, discharged and weighed. The organic and aqueous layers are separated, weighed and collected for further treatment. The organic layer is washed, dried and distilled out to remove colour. The catalyst is recycled back.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process developed replaces the existing sulfuric acid catalyzed esterification process. The catalyst is environmental friendly and is recyclable. The product yield is 99%.

Technology status:

An agreement for Basic Design Report (BDR) for Commercial Plant of 10 TPD was signed with M/s VOL, Mumbai. The process was demonstrated at bench scale in June 2014. The Designs for Commercial Plant of 5 TPD capacity were submitted in September 2015.

Patents: Provisional Patent applied to Indian Patent Office.

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CSIR – Indian Institute of Chemical Technology

Process for *para*-*tert*-butyl Toluene (PTBT)

Executive Summary

- A process for *para*-*tert*-butyl toluene (PTBT) based on alkylation of toluene is developed.
- *para*-*tert*-butyl toluene is widely used as solvent and as an intermediate in organic synthesis and pharmaceuticals.
- The process is normally catalyzed by strong minerals or Lewis acids which have both environmental and industrial related problems. In addition to this, the process always involves formation of undesired isomers of alkylated aromatics.
- The developed process is based on continuous addition of H₂SO₄ and bubbling of isobutylene gas through toluene under mild reaction conditions to get selectively *para* isomer with high conversion.

Background

The current demand of PTBT in the Indian market is solely met through imports. The aforesaid product is manufactured and supplied by Chinese Companies (the annual demand and prices of the products are as per requirement). At present, PTBT is not manufactured at large scale by the Indian industry. M/s VOL, Mumbai is producing isobutylene at their manufacturing site and would like to utilize the isobutylene for the production of value added chemicals. The process developed at CSIR-IICT is by alkylation of toluene using isobutylene gas to get selectively *para*-*tert* butyl toluene in the presence of a catalyst under mild reaction conditions. Key features are described in the following.

Process description

The process developed by CSIR-IICT consists of reacting toluene with isobutylene in the presence of a catalyst.

Salient features/ Advantages over competing processes

The process developed for the continuous production of *para*-*tert*-butyl toluene (PTBT) with 80% conversion and 99% selectivity towards *para* isomer.

Technology status:

The process was developed at bench scale and demonstrated to M/s VOL in a semi-batch mode in March 2013. Subsequently an agreement for scale-up studies and Basic Design Report (BDR) for continuous Commercial Plant of 12 TPD for *para*-*tert*-butyl toluene was signed. The designs for a pilot plant for a capacity of 5kg/h were submitted to the client. Based on the designs a pilot scale assembly for continuous alkylation was erected at IICT premises. The pilot scale demonstration was completed in February 2014. Data for BDR for a Commercial Plant of 12 TPD capacity was generated at pilot scale. The Designs for Commercial Plant completed and BDR submitted in June 2014.

Patents: Provisional Patent applied to Indian Patent Office.

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CSIR – Indian Institute of Chemical Technology

Annexure 2: List of Book
chapters/ Publications/
Patents/ Disclosures/
Conference Presentations

Book Chapters based on Indus MAGIC work

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77. Invited lecture –Structural and mechanistic understanding of catalytic reactions – Key to design new materials, Kannan Srinivasan, 16th National Workshop on Catalysis for Sustainable Development, CSIR-NEERI, Nagpur February 4-5, 2014.
78. Aqueous mediated Henry reaction by novel binuclear catalysts, R.Arunachalam and P.S.Subramanian, Presented at 16th CRSI –RSC Symposium at IIT Mumbai, Feb 7 -9, 2014 (Conference Paper).
79. Chemo- and regioselective synthesis of arylated γ -valerolactones from biomass derived levulinic acid using β -zeolite as catalyst, Sreedhar Gundekari and Kannan Srinivasan, Oral presentation at International Conference on Sustainable Chemistry and Engineering (SusChemE) held at Hotel Lalit, Mumbai during October 8-9, 2015 (as a prelude to APCAT-7; Best Oral Presentation Award for Sreedhar - Second Prize).
80. Selective hydrogenation of Cinnamaldehyde to Cinnamyl Alcohol, Amol M. Garkhedkar, Savita K. Shingote, Vilas H. Rane, Ashutosh A. Kelkar, Vivek V. Ranade, Poster Presented at CATSYMP 22, CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, January, 2015 and IndusMagic Workshop, CSIR-NCL, Pune, December 2013 and 2015
81. G. Thennarasu and A. Sivasamy*, Mn doped ZnO Nanomaterial: A highly visible light active photocatalyst for environmental abatement, Paper Presented at International Conference on Nanomaterials and Nanotechnology (NANO-2015) held at KSR college of technology, Tiruchengode from 07-10 December, 2015.
82. Saranya Ramachandran and A. Sivasamy*, *Synthesis Of Nanocrystalline Bismuth Oxide And Its Visible Photocatalytic Activity In The Degradation Of An Organic Dye* _Presented at International Conference on Nanomaterials and Nanotechnology (NANO-2015) held at KSR college of technology, Tiruchengode from 07-10 December, 2015.
83. Kulkarni, A. A., Scale-up of flow reactors, (Flow Chemistry India, January, 2015, Mumbai)
84. Design of Solid Catalyst for the Transformation of Glycerol to Glycidol via Glycerol Carbonate, Sunil Gilani, S.C. Ghosh, Poster presented at CATSYMP 22 held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar during January 7-9, 2015 and at 17th CRSI National Symposium in Chemistry, held at CSIR-NCL, Pune during February 6-8 2015.
85. Solid base hydrotalcite catalyst in the effective condensation of 1-octanal and benzaldehyde for selective synthesis of alpha-hexyl cinnamaldehyde. Jacky H. Adwani and Ram S. Shukla, Poster presented at 22nd National Symposium on Catalysis (CATSYMP 22) held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, India during 7-9 January 2015.
86. Diastereoselective nitroaldol reaction catalyzed by binuclear copperII complexes in aqueous medium, R. Arunachalam, C.S. Aswathi, Anjan Das, R.I. Kureshy and P.S. Subramanian, Poster presented at 22nd National Symposium on Catalysis, held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, India during 7-9 January 2015.
87. 16. Preparation of functionalized castor oil derivatives using heterogeneous catalysts, S. Sivashunmugam, Kannan Srinivasan, Oral presentation at 22nd National Symposium on Catalysis held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, India during 7-9, January 2015 (Abs. P. No. OP-51, p. 174).
88. Liquid phase oxidation of p-cymene catalysed by CoAl and CoMnAl layered double hydroxides in methanolic medium, Dakhra Bhavesh, Kannan Srinivasan, Poster presentation at 22nd National Symposium on Catalysis held at CSIR- CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, India during 7-9, January 2015 (Abs. P. No. PP-163, p. 527).
89. Selective hydrogenation of methyl ricinoleate to ricinoleyl alcohol over heterogeneous catalysts: Status, attempts and challenges, Gaurav Kumar, Kannan Srinivasan, Poster presentation at 22nd National Symposium on Catalysis held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, India during 7-9, January 2015 (Abs. P. No. PP-162, p. 525).

90. An Efficient Catalytic Protocol for the Synthesis of Rosy Fragrant-Mefrosol, Sekhar Nandi, N. H. Khan, R. I. Kureshy, S.H.R. Abdi, H. C. Bajaj, Poster presentation at 22nd National Symposium on Catalysis held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, India during 7-9, January 2015.
91. An invited talk titled "Biomass to fuels and chemicals: A journey through oleochemistry" given by Dr. Kannan Srinivasan at the '22nd National Symposium on Catalysis (CATSYMP 22) held at CSIR-CSMCRI, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India during 7-9 January, 2015.
92. Selective synthesis of alpha-hexyl cinnamaldehyde using eco-friendly solid base catalyst, Jacky H. Adwani, Ram S. Shukla, Poster presentation at Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (IndusBCP) held at Hotel Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, Gujarat during 8-9 May 2015.
93. Dehydration of 2-octanol to selectively form 1-octene over solid acid catalysts, Bhadrash Pandya and Kannan Srinivasan, Poster presentation at Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (IndusBCP) held at Hotel Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, Gujarat during 8-9 May 2015.
94. Liquid phase oxidation of p-cymene catalyzed by heterogeneous catalysts, Bhavesh Dakhra and Kannan Srinivasan, Poster presentation at Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (IndusBCP) held at Hotel Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, Gujarat during 8-9 May 2015.
95. Cyclamenaldehyde production from 4-isopropylbenzaldehyde, G. Sampath and Kannan Srinivasan, Poster presentation at Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (IndusBCP) held at Hotel Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, Gujarat during 8-9 May 2015.
96. R&D at CSIR-CSMCRI – A Glance with Emphasis on Inorganic Materials and Catalysis, H.C. Bajaj, Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (Indus BCP) held at Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, during May 8-9, 2015 under Indus MAGIC program.
97. Process Intensification: Create & Retain Competitive Edge, Vivek. V. Ranade, Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (Indus BCP) held at Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, during May 8-9, 2015 under Indus MAGIC program.
98. Asymmetric Catalysis Research at CSIR-CSMCRI – A Journey of Two Decades, N.H. Khan, Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (Indus BCP) held at Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, during May 8-9, 2015 under Indus MAGIC program.
99. Solid acid catalysts –Viable and Eco-friendly Alternative for Fine and Specialty Chemicals, Beena Tyagi, Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (Indus BCP) held at Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, during May 8-9, 2015 under Indus MAGIC program.
100. Catalysis Research on Perfumery Chemicals at CSIR-CSMCRI, Kannan Srinivasan, Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (Indus BCP) held at Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, during May 8-9, 2015 under Indus MAGIC program.
101. Four more posters on mefrosol, dioctylphthate, glycidol and green brominating agent mediated oxidation reactions have been presented presentation at Industrial Workshop on Benign Catalytic Processes for Fine and Speciality Chemicals (IndusBCP) held at Hotel Lords Plaza, Ankleshwar, Gujarat during 8-9 May 2015.
102. Development of green catalytic technologies and synthetic protocols for valorisation of lignocellulose derived levulinic acid, Sreedhar Gundekari and Kannan Srinivasan, Poster presented at 3rd International Symposium on Green Chemistry (ISGC), La Rochelle, France during May 3-7, 2015 (Abstract No. 570).
103. Snehal D. Hadawale, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, Sunil S. Joshi and Vivek V. Ranade., "Synthesis, Characterization and Application of Polyaluminum Chloride Coagulant: Treatment of Dye Wastewater", Presented at National Conference on Frontiers in Chemical and Material Sciences- FCMS-2015, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Jan 16-17, 2015. **(Best Paper Presentation Award)**
104. Anamika Pund, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, V. S. Patil and Vivek V. Ranade., "Newer adsorbents and cavitation intensified process for dye wastewater treatment", International Conference on Environment and Ecology- ICEE-2015, Kolkata, 2-4 March, 2015.
105. Vinay M. Bhandari, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam and Vivek V. Ranade, "Industrial wastewater treatment for fertilizer industry- A case study", International Conference – Industrial waste and wastewater treatment and valorisation; IWWATV 2015, Athens, Greece 21-23 May, 2015 (2015)*.
106. Reddi Kamesh, Rani K Y, Experimental vapour liquid equilibrium data for a binary mixture of dimethyl carbonate (1) + anisole (2) and thermodynamic modeling using Modified-UNIFAC group contribution method, International Conference on New Frontiers in Chemical, Energy And Environmental Engineering, INCEEE-2015, March 20-21, 2015, NIT Warangal, Paper No. 49, 2015
107. Varaprasad N B, Rani K Y, Modeling and analysis of a Novel Membrane Reactor to integrate Hydrogenation and Dehydrogenation Reactions, International Conference on New Frontiers in Chemical, Energy And Environmental Engineering, INCEEE-2015, March 20-21, 2015, NIT Warangal, Paper No. 174, 2015
108. P. Anand , B. Bhaskar, Optimal control of a polymerization reactor using Iterative dynamic programming , International Conference on New Frontiers in Chemical, Energy And Environmental Engineering, INCEEE-2015, March 20-21, 2015, NIT Warangal, Paper No. 283, 2015
109. Dutt, N. V. K, Chandra S. L, Reddi K, Ravi Kumar Y. V. L., Rani, K. Y., Estimation of BOD to COD ratio of organic compounds using specific refraction, molecular number and electro negativity, International Conference on Advances in Chemical Engineering (ICACE 2015), Dec 20-22, 2015, NIT Suratkal, Paper No. 226, 2015

110. Siddharth, M. S. G, Teja, V., Reddi K , Rani K. Y., Simulation Study on Separation of Phenol and O-Cresol by Azeotropic Distillation, CHEMCON 2015, Dec 27-30, 2015, Guwahati, Paper No. MS-072, 2015
111. SD Hadawale, LG Sorokhaibam, VM Bhandari, SS Joshi and VV Ranade, Synthesis, Characterization and Application of Polyaluminum Chloride Coagulant: Treatment of Dye Wastewater, National Conference on Frontiers in Chemical and Material Sciences- FCMS-2015
112. S Nagpure, A Pund, LG Sorokhaibam, VM Bhandari and VV Ranade, Application of Adsorption Process in Desulfurization and Wastewater Treatment, Presented at OPRD Workshop, NCL Pune, 4-5 December, 2014 and National Conference on Frontiers in Chemical and Material Sciences- FCMS-2015 [Best paper award], 2015
113. P Suryawanshi, LG Sorokhaibam, VM Bhandari, JP Ruparelia and VV Ranade , Hydrodynamic Cavitation for Degradation of Solvents from Industrial Wastewater, Presented at OPRD Workshop, NCL Pune, 4-5 December, 2014 and Science Day Poster Presentations, NCL Pune, 25-26 February, 2015 and International Conference on New Frontiers in Chemical, Energy and Environmental Engineering (INCEEE-2015), NIT Warangal, 20-21 March, 2015
114. Vinay M. Bhandari, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam and Vivek V. Ranade. Hydrodynamic Cavitation for Distillery Wastewater Treatment. *Proceedings of XI Joint Convention of STAI/DSTA*, 4-6 September, 2015
115. Anamika Pund, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, V. S. Patil and Vivek V. Ranade, Newer adsorbents and cavitation intensified process for dye wastewater treatment, International Conference on New Frontiers in Chemical, Energy and Environmental Engineering (INCEEE-2015), 2015
116. Pravin B. Patil, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari, V. S. Patil and Vivek V. Ranade, Removal of Ammoniacal Nitrogen from Industrial Wastewaters- Process Intensification for Degradation of 4-amino Phenol using Hydrodynamic Cavitation, Presented at International Conference on New Frontiers in Chemical, Energy and Environmental Engineering (INCEEE-2015) [Best paper award], 2015 and National Conference on Frontiers in Chemical and Material Sciences- FCMS-2015, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Jan 16-17, 2015. **(Best Paper Award)**
117. Krati Sharma, Chethana M., Vinay M. Bhandari, Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vivek V. Ranade, Deepak J. Killedar. Application of bio-coagulants in dye wastewater treatment - Development of a new cavitation methodology using cavitation and coagulation. in 6th World Congress on Biotechnology, New Delhi, 5-7 October, 2015
118. Kushal R. Rane, Vinay M. Bhandari, Vilas S. Patil and Vivek V. Ranade. Degradation of Polyvinyl Alcohol using Hydrodynamic Cavitation., in Royal Chemical Society-WIS symposium, "Frontiers of Advances in Chemistry and Technology -2015 (FACT-2015)" 11-12 Dec. 2015, NMU Jalgaon
119. K. Dimya, J. U. Sarode, V. M. Bhandari and V. V. Ranade. Isolation and graft polymerization of nanocrystals from cellulose. in Royal Chemical Society-WIS symposium , "Frontiers of Advances in Chemistry and Technology -2015 (FACT-2015)" 11-12 Dec. 2015, NMU Jalgaon (2015). **(BEST POSTER award in Faculty Section)**
120. Jayashri U. Sarode, K. Dimya, Vinay M. Bhandari, R. S. Shirsam and Vivek V. Ranade. Newer adsorbent modifications for application in dye wastewater treatment. in Royal Chemical Society-WIS symposium , "Frontiers of Advances in Chemistry and Technology -2015 (FACT-2015)" 11-12 Dec. 2015, NMU Jalgaon (2015). **(BEST POSTER award in Post-Graduate Student Section)**
121. Laxmi Gayatri Sorokhaibam, Vinay M. Bhandari , Monal S. Salvi , Saijal Jain , Snehal D. Hadawale and Vivek V. Ranade. New adsorbent from Cassia fistula for process separations & wastewater treatment. In Workshop on Intensification & Upscaling of Continuous Processes: December 11-12, 2015
122. Chirag Khalde and VV Ranade, CFD simulations of AMAR micro-mixer cum reactor, European mixing conference to be held at St Petersburg, June 2015
123. DV Sharma and VV Ranade, Estimation of Gas Induction in Jet Loop Reactors: Influence of Nozzle Designs, Gas-liquid-solid Reactor Engineering (GLS 12) to be held at New York, June 2015
124. AV Pandit and VV Ranade, Heat & Mass Transfer in Boiling and Reacting Gas-Liquid Systems: A Study of Isolated Droplets & Bubbles, Gas-liquid-solid Reactor Engineering (GLS 12) to be held at New York, June 2015
125. Reddi K , Rani K. Y., Adaptive ANN Model based Nonlinear Control of a Semi-batch Polymerization Reactor Challenge Problem, Indian Control Conference (ICC - 2016), Jan 4-6th 2016, Hyderabad, Paper No. 59, 2016.
126. Anand P., Reddi K , Rani K. Y., Evaluation of Control Strategies for a Semi Batch Copolymerization Reactor, Indian Control Conference (ICC - 2016), Jan 4-6th 2016, Hyderabad, Paper No. 98, 2016.
127. Kumar, N. P., Prathyusha N., Reddi K , Rani K. Y., Intensified Process for the Separation of a Multicomponent Mixture using Divided Wall Column, Proceedings of National Seminar on "Process Intensification in Process Industries-(PI)2", 25th – 26th March 2016, Paper No. 2, 2016
128. Shireesha, M., Krishna, V. A., Kumar, P. M., Rani K. Y., Development of a Kinetic Model for a Reaction with Mass Transfer: An Esterification Case Study, Proceedings of National Seminar on "Process Intensification in Process Industries-(PI)2", 25th – 26th March 2016, Paper No. 3, 2016
129. Kumar, S., Dharshini, S. D., Reddi K , Rani K. Y., Sensitivity Analysis for Reactive Distillation of Methyl-Tert-Butyl Ether Production, Proceedings of National Seminar on "Process Intensification in Process Industries-(PI)2", 25th – 26th March 2016, Paper No. 33, 2016
130. G. Meenakshi and A. Sivasamy*, Photocatalytic degradation of Resorcinol by ZnO/SiC nanocomposites under visible light irradiation, Presented at National conference on innovations in chemical sciences (NCIC-2016) held at Guru Nanak College, Chennai-42 from 28-30 January, 2016.
131. Kulkarni, A. A. Dispersed phase (drobble: drop-bubble) dynamics in a boiling stirred tank reactor, Eu Mixing Conference, St. Petersburg (Russia)
132. Kulkarni, A. A.; Residence time distribution of solids in microchannels, IMRET13, Budapest, Hungary

Annexure 3: MAGIC Team

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CSIR - NCL	
	Dr Vivek V. Ranade , Outstanding Scientist, vv.ranade@ncl.res.in Research interests: Chemical & reactor engineering, multiphase flows, multi-scale modeling; Process intensification for sustainable chemical industry, process development and scale-up; Waste water treatment, enhancing performance of anaerobic digesters; Innovation, technology management, start-up companies
	Dr Sunil S. Joshi , Senior Principal Scientist, ss.joshi@ncl.res.in Research interests: Process intensification for sustainable chemical industry, Process development and scale-up, Conversion of batch processes to continuous, Chemical reactions in supercritical fluids, Conversion of biomass and carbon dioxide to useful chemicals, catalysis, Technology transfer
	Dr Vinay M. Bhandari , Senior Principal Scientist, vm.bhandari@ncl.res.in Research interests: Chemical & reactor engineering, Separation Science & Technology, Biotechnology, Industrial Process improvements, Process intensification, Wastewater Treatment, Environmental Pollution Control
	Dr Amol A. Kulkarni , Pr. Scientist, aa.kulkarni@ncl.res.in Research interests: chemical reaction engineering, microreactors, flow chemistry, process development, design of flow reactors, batch to continuous transformation, experimental and computational fluid dynamics, synthesis and scale-up of nanomaterials, analysis of product portfolio.
	Mr Yogesh S. Suryawanshi , Scientist, ys.suryawanshi@ncl.res.in Research Interests: Chemical & Reactor Engineering, Multiphase Flows, Separation, Pilot plant (scale up, design & construction), modular chemical plants, 3D Design, Prototyping, Product Development, Composite material application, laboratory & Facility Design, Scratch & Scale model building, Innovation & Entrepreneurship
	Dr Sanjay P. Kamble , Senior Scientist, sp.kamble@ncl.res.in Research Interests: Process intensification, Process development and scaleup, Photocatalysis of energy and environmental applications, treatment of wastewater by AOPs and microalgae/MBR techniques.
	Dr Ashutosh A. Kelkar , Senior Principal Scientist, aa.kelkar@ncl.res.in Research Interest: Homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis, Carbonylation, hydroformylation and hydrogenation reactions, Transesterification reactions, Glycerol to value added products, Asymmetric transfer hydrogenation of ketones and imines.
	Dr Vilas H. Rane , Principal Scientist, vh.rane@ncl.res.in Research interests: Homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis, oxidative conversion of lower and higher alkanes, high pressure oxidation and hydrogenation reactions, glycerol to value added products, dehydrogenation reactions, trans-esterification reactions
	Dr Rajnish Kumar , Senior Scientist, k.rajnish@ncl.res.in Research interests: Un-conventional energy resources, Gas hydrates, CO ₂ capture & storage, Process development and scale-up of fine chemicals, High pressure reactions.
	Dr A Sudalai , Sr. Principal Scientist, a.sudalai@ncl.res.in Research interests: Asymmetric synthesis of drugs and natural products <i>via</i> metal and organo catalysis, synthetic methods via heterogeneous and homogeneous catalysis, chiral catalysis, CO ₂ reduction and C-H bond activation of alkanes using metal catalysts and development of synthetic methods.

Annexure 3: MAGIC Team

CSIR - IICT	
	Dr K. Rajender Reddy , Principal Scientist, rajender@iict.res.in Research interests: Developing metal- and metal- free (organo) catalysts in chemo-, regio- and stereo- selective organic transformations. Developing new catalysts, mechanistic studies and utilization of catalysts in organic transformations
	Dr N Lingaiah , Principal Scientist, nakkalingaiah@iict.res.in Research interests: Heterogeneous Catalysis. Metal/metal oxide catalysts, Heteropoly acids, Catalytic conversion biomass, Utilization of renewable resources; Environmental catalysis, Surface science, Operando spectroscopy
	Dr A Venugopal , Principal Scientist, akula@iict.res.in Research interests: Effective utilization of biomass derived byproducts, Development of catalysts for COx free hydrogen production, low temperature CO oxidation and WGS. Operando IR spectroscopy.
	Dr K. Yamuna Rani , Senior Principal Scientist, kyrani@iict.res.in Research interests: Dynamic modeling of nonlinear processes, data-driven modeling, Nonlinear model predictive control, multi-objective optimal control, development of alternate neural network modeling structures and schemes, kinetic modeling, physical properties estimation and prediction
	Dr C. Sumana , Principal Scientist, sumana@iict.res.in Research interests: Modelling, Optimization, State estimation and Inferential control of Chemical and Biochemical Processes, Advanced process monitoring and Fault diagnosis, scale up, kinetic modelling, Statistical Modelling & Analysis
	Dr P. Anand , Scientist, anandp@iict.res.in Research interests: Process Systems Engineering : Process Dynamics and control, Process modelling, Process Optimization – Static & Dynamic, Online optimizing control of batch processes, Evolutionary computation; Process development.
	Dr. B. Satyavathi , Principal Scientist, satya@iict.res.in Research interests: Process development, design and intensification for chemical and biochemical processes, Process improvements
	Dr Pravin R Likhari , Principal Scientist, plikhar@iict.res.in Research interests: Homogeneous catalysis and organometallic chemistry, Development of new heterogeneous catalysts and their applications, Green chemical reactions, Process development & scale-up, and Process intensification for sustainable chemical industry.
	Dr. T. Prathap Kumar , Principal Scientist, prathap@iict.res.in Research interests: Process Development and Process Design for technology transfer involving studies at bench scale and pilot scale, and Design of Commercial plants. Risk analysis, HAZOP studies and Disaster control and management plans for chemical process industries. Reactive extraction of organic acids.

Annexure 3: MAGIC Team

CSIR - CSMCRI	
	<p>Dr. H.C. Bajaj, Chief Scientist, hcbajaj@csmcri.org Research interest: Inorganic materials and their application for gas storage, nano composite, Catalysis, Kinetics and Mechanism, Coordination complexes and their use as homogeneous catalysts, Metal recovery from spent catalysts, Clay modification, Kimberlite value-addition, Nanoclay and applications in drug delivery</p>
	<p>Dr. S.H.R. Abdi, Chief Scientist, shrabdi@csmcri.org Research interest: Asymmetric organic transformations; Monomer synthesis for synthesis of chiral polymers; CO₂ to fuels and chemicals</p>
	<p>Dr. R.I. Kureshy, Sr. Principal Scientist, rkureshy@csmcri.org Research interest: Chiral transition metal complexes for asymmetric organic transformations; Catalysis for perfumery chemicals; CO₂ to fuels and chemicals</p>
	<p>Dr. Kannan Srinivasan, Sr. Principal Scientist, skannan@csmcri.org Research interest: Layered Double Hydroxides (LDHs); Biomass to chemicals and fuels (including polymers); Solid base catalysis; Catalysis for perfumery chemicals; C-C bond forming reactions; Catalytic conversion of CO₂ to chemicals; LDHs for waste water remediation; Solid state transformation of LDHs to oxides and carbonates</p>
	<p>Dr. N.H. Khan, Sr. Principal Scientist, nhkhan@csmcri.org Research interest: Chiral transition metal complexes for asymmetric organic transformations; Catalysis for perfumery chemicals; CO₂ to fuels and chemicals</p>
	<p>Dr. P.S. Subramanian, Principal Scientist, siva@csmcri.org Research interest: Novel chiral complexes and its catalytic applications in various asymmetric reactions, Luminescent complexes and its applications in biological investigation and display materials</p>
	<p>Dr. Beena Tyagi, Principal Scientist, bttyagi@csmcri.org Research interest: Heterogeneous catalysis; nano-crystalline mesoporous materials; green synthesis of industrially important molecules; structure-activity co-relation; zirconia based materials; zeolites; acid clays</p>
	<p>Dr. S. Adimurthy, Principal Scientist, adimurthy@csmcri.org Research interest: Organic synthesis, Synthesis of heterocycles, Green synthesis and Catalysis, Method developments, Green Halogenations, Functional modifications, Amide Synthesis, C-H functionalization, Oxidation reactions, Esterifications</p>
	<p>Dr. A.B. Panda, Sr. Scientist, abpanda@csmcri.org Research interest: Development of synthetic strategies for nanostructure materials comprising metals, metal sulfides and selenides, pure and mixed metal oxides; Use of the synthesized materials as catalyst, ion-exchange for environmental remediation, anode material for lithium-ion batteries and drug delivery</p>
	<p>Dr. S. C. Ghosh, Scientist, scghosh@csmcri.org Research interest: Organic transformations with special focus on Homogeneous, Heterogeneous Catalysts; Catalytic C-H Bond Functionalization; Development of new catalysts for C-C, C-O and C-N bond formation; Organic reactions in water; Asymmetric Synthesis; Molecular Transporters for Drug Delivery</p>

Annexure 3: MAGIC Team

CSIR - CLRI	
	<p>Dr A Sivasamy, Senior Principal Scientist, arumugamsivasamy@yahoo.co.in Research interests: Nano Materials and Applications, Photocatalysis, Catalysis and Sustainable Chemistry, Wastewater treatment, Advanced Oxidation Process, Adsorption dynamics, Waste minimization and utilization, polymer nano composites, Bioremediation for Organics.</p>
	<p>Dr C. Lajpathi Rai, Sr. Principal Scientist, clrai@clri.res.in Research interests: Ways of innovation for the reduction of excess sludge, Wastewater treatment and bio-energy generation (MFC & Biogas) with excess sludge reduction, Wet sludge mechanical disintegration to accelerate aerobic and anaerobic process.</p>
	<p>Dr. D. Murugan, Scientist, dmurugan@clri.res.in Research interests: Waste recycling, Wastewater treatment, Process intensification, Process equipment design, Oil well stimulation</p>
CSIR - NIIST	
	<p>Dr S. Savithri, Senior Principal Scientist, ssavithri@niist.res.in, sivakumarsavi@gmail.com Research interests: Multi-scale, multiphase modeling of reactors, processes, Technical software development, solidification modeling</p>

Two prominent team members superannuated before March 2016	
	<p>Dr M Lakshmi Kantam, Ex Director, CSIR - IICT, lkmanepalli@gmail.com Research interests: Developing catalytic processes for chemical industries under benign conditions; Design and development of new multifunctional catalytic materials; Understand the role of catalysts on their performance/deactivation through spectroscopic and microscopic tools</p>
	<p>Dr R.A. Joshi, Ex Chief Scientist, CSIR - NCL, ra.joshi@ncl.res.in Research interests: Development of continuous flow processes for pharmaceuticals intermediates and dyes, Process development for API, Fine chemicals</p>

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